

ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP
(CONCESSION) ON SERVICE DELIVERY OF THE NIGERIAN PORTS: A CASE
STUDY OF TIN CAN ISLAND PORT, LAGOS STATE

BY

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NIGERIA.

DECEMBER, 2022

DECLARATION

I declare that this dissertation entitled “Assessment of the Impact of Public-Private Partnership (Concession) on Service Delivery of Nigerian Ports: A Case Study of Tin Can Island Port, Lagos State” has been done by me in the Department of Political Science and International Studies, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The information derived from the literature has been duly acknowledged in the text and a list of references provided. No part of this thesis was previously presented for another degree or diploma at this or any other institution.

Muideen Olakunle MOHAMMED

CERTIFICATION

This dissertation entitled ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP (CONCESSION) ON SERVICE DELIVERY OF NIGERIAN PORTS: A CASE STUDY OF TIN CAN ISLAND PORT, LAGOS STATE by Muideen Olakunle Mohammed meets the regulations governing the award of the degree of Master of Science of the Ahmadu Bello University, and is approved for its contribution to knowledge and literary presentation.

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my late Mum, for not raising a quitter and being a perfect example on the importance of hard work.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AOMS	Airport Operations Management System
ATAT	Average Turnaround Time
BOT	Build Operate Transfer
BPE	Bureau of Public Enterprise
BPSR	Bureau of Public Service Reforms
CAC	Customs Area Controller
CBN	Central Bank of Nigeria
CET	Common External Tariff
CM	Concession Model
DBB	Design Bid Build
DEA	Data Envelopment Analysis
EOI	Expression of Interest
FAAN	Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria
FEPA	Federal Environmental Protection Agency
FOREX	Foreign Exchange
FSL	Five Star Logistics Limited
GAT	General Aviation Terminal
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GRT	Gross Registered Tonnage
GVA	Gross Value Added
ICRC	Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission
ILO	International Labour Organisation

JPS	Josepdam Ports Services Limited
KLT	Kirikiri Lighter Terminal
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCC	Lekki Concession Company Limited
LSDPC	Lagos State Property Development Commission
LSETF	Lagos State Employment Trust Fund
MDA	Ministries, Departments and Agencies
MMA	Murtala Muhammed Airport
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NAFDAC	National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control
NBS	National Bureau of Statistics
NCP	National Council on Privatization
NCS	Nigeria Customs Service
NDLEA	National Drug Law Enforcement Agency
NESREA	National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency
NICIS	Nigeria Integrated Customs Information System
NIMASA	Nigeria Maritime Administration and Safety Agency
NIS	Nigeria Immigration Service
NNPC	Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation
NPA	Nigerian Ports Authority
NPM	New Public Management
NSC	Nigerian Shippers Council
NSW	National Single Window

PCHS	Ports and Cargo Handling Services Limited
PEBEC	Presidential Enabling Business Environment Council
PPIAF	Public-Private Investment Advisory Facility
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
PSP	Private Sector Participation
PTML	Port and Terminal Multiservices Limited
RoRo	Roll-On-Roll-Off
RTG	Rubber Tyred Gantry
SAP	Structural Adjustment Programme
SON	Standards Organization of Nigeria
TEU	Twenty-foot Equivalent Unit
TCIP	Tin Can Island Port
TCIPC	Tin Can Island Port Complex
TCPC	Technical Committee on Privatisation and Commercialisation
UNCTAD	United Nations Conference on Trade and Development
VfM	Value for Money
WBG	World Bank Group
WDI	World Development Indicators
WSC	World Shipping Council

ABSTRACT

Public-Private Partnership (PPP) has become a public policy decision used by the government to provide funding and needed expertise for infrastructure development and improve service delivery in public sectors. Nigeria practices PPP using the concession model for some of its major infrastructure projects. This research identified four major problems of the Nigerian ports – Centralization of NPA’s authority, Constant change of port governance model, Procedures for Cargo clearance, and Inaccessible roads – which affected service delivery at the ports before the adoption of PPP. This research aims to fill conceptual and empirical gaps in unilateral study of port. The research chose New Public Management (NPM) theory over Neoliberalism theory due to NPM’s assumptions which give managerial and organizational structure to projects, and still promote business practices, cutback on bureaucratic practices, the introduction of user charges and contracting out services to the private sector. It used the mixed research method to collect primary and secondary data from the Tin Can Island Port (TCIP). Secondary data (annual reports) was aggregated to measure port performance before and after concession using growth rate analysis while primary sources of data (questionnaires and interviews) were triangulated to analyze the impacts of PPP on TCIP’s service delivery and port performance. The findings showed there were positive and negative impact of concession on port performance, challenges like cargo clearance procedure and high charges, cargo transportation to/from port areas, the inadequacy of equipment and the inaccessible road to TCIP and its terminals still affects port operations. It recommended policy measures like hastening up rehabilitation of port roads and alternate transport to reduce congestion and traffic; provision of needed equipment at port terminals by NPA, Customs and federal government; make the NPA’s National Single Window (NSW) platform operative to reduce delay in cargo clearance; and implementation of proactive policy to clear out people traffic and illegal business in port areas to improve service delivery.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

In recent times, infrastructure development had a renewed drive in Nigeria's master-plan to attain economic growth and development, federal and state governments formulated and implemented public policy decisions that will bring out change in infrastructure development or provision of essential services. For instance, federal government's renewed drive has been focused on developing infrastructure from construction of the Kaduna-Abuja railway, reconstruction of Abuja-Kaduna-Kano highway to building low-cost housing such as the Gwarinpa II Estate in Abuja and other capital projects as a pact to achieving sustainable growth and development.

The prioritization of infrastructural development is the core policy for successive administration. During the early period of post-colonial Nigeria, there were four National Development Plans – the First National Development Plan (1962 – 1968); the Second National Development Plan (1970 – 1974); the Third National Development Plan (1975–1980) and the Fourth National Development Plan (1981–1985) – which focused on improving infrastructure development in Agricultural, Energy, Transport, Health, Education and Industrial sectors (Uche, 2019). At the time when the second national development plan was being implemented in 1970, Nigeria's oil boom era kicked-off as revenue from oil production rose which was ₦1.8 million in 1958 rose to ₦1.058 billion in 1970 and increased to over 5.365 billion naira in 1975 (Mohammed, 2010).

The increase in oil revenue in the 1970s gave the government unfettered access to revenue to boost each sector of the economy to become self-sufficient as well as be able to provide the citizens with social services but some of these improvement witnessed in these sectors began

to dwindle due to: the politicization of governmental policies such as indigenization policy of 1972; obvious maladministration and mismanagement of the 1979 Green Revolution Programme; allegation of unchecked corruption within the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) in 1979; public sector dominance of infrastructure financing with the second national development plan 1970-1974; and subsequent global fall in oil price in late 1970 (Ugoani, 2017; Uche, 2019).

Consequently, some of the infrastructure projects embarked upon in the period of the National Development Plans between 1962 to 1985 became obsolete, moribund, and dysfunctional as a result of the neglect which occurred when there was no more revenue to fund these projects and the subsequent economic crisis around early 1980s moved it from bad to worse even after the austerity measures that civilian and military government had to resort to during the period (Akinwale & Aremo, 2010). The adoption and implementation of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) which had slight impact on infrastructural development in the country with funding from aids and grants but corruption, mismanagement, excessive bureaucracy as well as political instability (Uche, 2019) marred the process of any meaningful development in public infrastructure.

Ikeanyibe (2009) noted that SAP presented a policy-based approach for reevaluating the country's planning system and reduction of public expenditure was one of the major highlights of SAP and since its implementation, the Nigerian state's ability to successfully finance the cost of expanding, improving and maintaining its public infrastructure has drastically declined.

The infrastructure in the country continued to deteriorate, some public enterprises had reached a state of disuse and low service delivery was inherent in government service sectors by May 1999 when civilian rule was restored to the country. As of late 1990s, Nigerian Ports were also caught in the web of this ineptitude as it demonstrated a relatively reduced level of efficiency,

resulting in long turnaround times for ships and increased container dwell time. Instead of the forty-eight hours international standard to unload and reload ship, it took weeks. The workforce was overstaffed; there were excessive port-related charges, and a massive level of cargo theft (Leigland & Palsson, 2007).

In a bid to address the issues plaguing port operations, concession was introduced to Nigerian ports to bring in needed expertise in the area of operations but the larger picture of ensuring infrastructural improvement and improved service delivery in Nigeria public enterprises began in 1999 when President Obasanjo's administration set the wheels of mass privatization into motion with Public Enterprises (Privatization and Commercialization) Act of 1999 which led to the establishment of the National Council on Privatization (NCP). The NCP prioritized port reforms after it was inaugurated in 1999, beginning with the request for funding from the World Bank's Public-Private Investment Advisory Facility (PPIAF) to study and formulate port sector reform strategy for the Federal Ministry of Transport, the grant was approved in early 2001 and a Dutch maritime advisory firm, Royal Haskoning BV, was engaged to prepare the assessment.

Haskoning study, as the report was popularly referred to, concluded that the administration of the Nigerian ports was characterized by an unusually high degree of centralization as the NPA was responsible for both regulations of port operations as well as the day-to-day operational decisions, hence, it was inclined to raise its prices to deal with internal budget deficits, instead of working to improve efficiency and productivity which led to repeated tariff increases, unchecked inefficiencies and poor governance, putting Nigerian ports among the slowest and most expensive in the world, despite being one of the largest in Africa (Leigland & Palsson, 2007).

The report recommended transitioning the port governance model to the landlord model through concession to private sector to manage operations as well as downsizing of workers by 75%, the Federal Government implemented these measures before it proceeded to concession the ports. It should be noted that the landlord model is a port governance model that transfers basic port infrastructure and services to private companies by means of some sort of lease or contractual arrangement to provide cargo-handling services. According to Nwanosike (2014), twenty-five concessions were identified from the eleven ports managed by the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) and twenty concession agreements were signed within a year.

Nigeria is amongst third-world countries that begun using public-private partnership (PPP) to fund its infrastructure deficit in the early twenty-first century which coincided with the period she returned to civilian rule in 1999. Since that period, the common types of PPP models used for executing projects are concessions, service contracts, management contracts and leases.

The process undertaken for port reforms in Nigeria can be likened to public policy making process, following the identification of a policy problem – that service delivery of the Nigerian ports was mismanaged, inefficient, overpriced, overstaffed and corrupt which had forward and backward linkages. The introduction of public-private partnerships in port reform was a public policy decision, albeit distributive and regulatory but made it efficient, plugged the leakages in the country's ports and improved service delivery (Olaniyi, 2016).

Tin Can Island Port (TCIP) used as a case study for this study is one of the two ports located in Lagos state and caters for five of the concessions handed over to private investors. The TCIP was commissioned in 1977 due to the increase in economic activities during the oil boom era coupled with the post-civil war reconstruction. However, the current TCIP is a fusion of Roll-On-Roll-Off (RoRo) terminals used majorly for automobile importations and the Tin Can Island Ports.

1.2 Statement of the Research Problem

The Nigerian ports, especially those in Lagos and Port-Harcourt were major drivers of the economy during the pre-colonial period and extended this feat into the post-independence era, especially the oil boom period when other ports were commissioned to meet up with the demand for petroleum products and other exports. This research identified four major problems of the Nigerian ports – Centralization of NPA’s authority, Constant change of port governance model, Procedures for Cargo clearance, and Inaccessible roads.

The centralization of NPA’s authority which involves day-to-day management of port terminals’ operations and performing regulatory functions had spillback effects on port performance. Constant change of port governance model has its effects too, from its inception, Nigerian ports practiced the Private Service model, moved to the Public Service model and was on the Tool Port model of administration before the reform of the port was launched. These models have shown that there are leakages in Nigerian ports administration, for instance, the tool port model revealed port security was porous and massive overstaffing.

Also, the procedures for cargo clearance at Nigerian ports were cumbersome as it was carried out manually while ships turnaround time was over a month which caused loss of cargoes due to bad warehouse services and high clearance charges. Beyond that, inaccessible roads to port areas affected transport of export cargoes and cleared containers at the port.

All the aforesaid problems led to the adoption of PPP in Nigerian ports, hence, this study examined TCIP in Lagos to analyze the impact of concession in curtailing these highlighted challenges, facilitate positive port performance and improve service delivery.

1.3 Research Questions

The study seeks to address the following questions.

- i. What were the challenges that affected the service delivery capacity at the TCIP before the adoption of PPP?
- ii. What has been the impact of the concession on service delivery at the TCIP?
- iii. What impact has the concession had on revenue generation at the TCIP?
- iv. What are the challenges still lurking around in port operation after the concession?

1.4 Aims and Objectives of the Study

The aims of the study includes the following.

- i. To determine the challenges encountered in the Nigerian ports before the adoption of PPP.
- ii. To examine the impacts of concession on service delivery TCIP's port terminals.
- iii. To assess the impact of PPP on revenue generation at the TCIP.
- iv. To examine the challenges faced in port operations after the adoption of PPP and proffer policy recommendations.

1.5 Research Assumptions

The research is based on the following assumptions.

- i. The adoption of PPP had a positive or negative impact on service delivery at TCIP.
- ii. The concession of the terminals enhanced cargo clearance procedures at TCIP.
- iii. The concession of TCIP increased revenue generation at the TCIP.

- iv. The concession of TCIP terminals improved infrastructural facilities within the port and its environs.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The research was conducted to fill the gaps identified in some literature and study on Nigerian ports. This study adds to growing research works on unilateral study of port complex in Nigeria.

The empirical research conducted on Nigerian ports mainly used secondary data from annual reports and observations to analyze the impact of concession, but this research was conducted using primary data collected from port users and personnel to measure growth rate of the TCIP.

This study used theoretical underpinnings to explain why government adopts PPP, what PPP model to adopt for public projects and how they decide on PPP projects to embark on.

Also, this study serves as a policy brief on the successes and mistakes of Nigeria's port concession.

1.7 Scope and Limitation of the Study

The six port complexes in Nigeria at present are all viable, but the research was conducted in one of the most viable ports, the Tin Can Island Port (TCIP) which shares the leading spot with its counterpart, the Apapa Port Complex, both located in Lagos State.

The research examined the PPP arrangement of the Nigerian ports. It should be noted that the landlord model is a port governance model that transfers basic port infrastructure and services to private companies by means of some sort of lease or contractual arrangement to provide cargo-handling services. Using the landlord model for Nigerian ports, the NPA will provide port infrastructure and superstructure including cargo handling equipment such as quay cranes and forklifts, which are operated by port authority staff but cargo handling onboard vessels,

aprons and quays are the responsibility of private terminal operators. Also, the terminal operators will be paying annual rent to NPA throughout the duration of the concession agreement.

The timeframe of the study covered the pre-concession period from 1999-2006 due to the unavailability of data before that period while the concession and post-concession period will be between 2007 and 2017. The rationale behind the post-concession timeline is that most of the concession contracts became effective and the private terminals became operational around late 2006, hence the need for a one-year window to balance handing over and other operational issues between the NPA and the private terminal operators. Also, the ten-year time frame is to examine the impact of PPP on service delivery at TCIP in the wake of the original ten years contract agreement for Josepdam and Five Star Logistics before it was extended by five (5) years in March 2014.

The study focuses majorly on TCIP's growth rate within the concession period using metrics such as cargo throughput, container throughput, vehicular traffic, turnaround time of vessels and berth occupancy rate of vessels. The research design made use of questionnaires, interviews and annual reports to collect data for empirical and thematic analysis of the impact of concession on TCIP's service delivery and operations.

During the collection of data from port users, the language barrier was a huge challenge with truck drivers as most of them couldn't read or speak English. Hence, the researcher employed the services of a postgraduate student in the Linguistics Department of the University of Ibadan to translate the questionnaires into Nigerian Pidgin and Yoruba, the most preferred language of the truck drivers. The translated questionnaire was administered to the respondents and they answered it perfectly, thus, there was no cross-lingual translation issue for the data gotten from the port users.

Setting up interviews with port personnel was a major issue during fieldwork, letter of introduction submitted to the correspondence room took two months before it was replied or found. At the private terminals, some principals declined the letters, while some got lost during filing and the reception was lukewarm. For instance, the researcher was not given access to ask interview staff at the NPA Headquarters in Marina but rather directed to TCIPC, stating that that was the focus of the study, hence, no questions will be entertained.

Also, the original list of interviewee included Managing Directors of the five private terminals, Managing Director of NPA, Port Manager at TCIP, Port Legal Adviser and the Customs Area Controller (CAC) of the NCS for the TCIP Command but due to the non-accessibility of some port personnel, another key staff was interviewed after appropriate redirection from these channels. The researcher was able to interview PA-PM on Operations at TCIP (to replace the Port Manager for TCIP); the PLA at TCP (who also doubles as the Chairman of Concession Committee); the Chief Port Tariff and Billing Officer (CTBO) of TCIP; the PRO for NCS for the TCIP Command (to replace the CAC).

Interviews with Managing Directors of Private Terminals was thwarted due to excessive bureaucracy and outright refusal to grant interviews by these principals but out of the five private terminal operators, only two of them was open for interview (FSL and JSL) and four personnel from these terminals granted audience to the researcher. Meanwhile, some interviewees at the private terminals declined recorded interviews and anonymity status, so the researcher had to write down responses given during the interview. Most notable, the inaccessible port roads was a huge challenge due to the high prices of transport to port areas which the researcher had to pay in order to get access to port areas.

1.8 Conceptual Clarification

Concepts such as Public Policy, Public-Private Partnership, Concession, and Service Delivery which are central to the subject under study are clearly defined.

1.8.1 Public-Private Partnership (PPP)

PPP is referred to as a contractual agreement, cooperation or alliance between the public sector represented by the government or its agencies and the private sector concern represented by business-oriented companies, individuals and global financial institutions to pull resources ranging from finance to expertise in formulating, designing, constructing, maintaining, managing, and sharing risks while providing new services to the general public or restructuring the services which the government has been providing to the public but needs to improve on its access, efficiency and quality.

1.8.2 Concession

According to Business Dictionary (2020), concession means granting of exclusive privileges (such as the right to be the only seller of a good or service) by a government authority or by the owner of a singular property (such as an airport, amusement park, hotel) to a grantee or concessionaire, who pays rent or a certain percentage of the sales or earnings to the grantor

1.8.3 Service Delivery

Service delivery is a common term used when transacting between two or more individuals. It refers to the interaction between providers and clients where the provider offers a service, in form of information or task and the client either finds value or loses value as a result of the service, when the client gets optimum satisfaction from the task or information provided by the provider, it is termed a good service delivery while the reverse is termed bad service delivery.

1.9 Chapter Organization

This research consists of five chapters, the first chapter is a general introduction which consists of background to the study, statement of the research problem, research questions, objectives of the study, research assumptions, significance of the study, scope of the study, conceptual clarification of public policy, PPP, concession and service delivery and chapter organization. Chapter Two is literature review and theoretical framework. The literature review included further conceptual clarification of public policy, PPP and concession, the importance of ports to nations and the Nigerian economy, comparing port governance and administration models used by countries with seaports, history of PPP in Nigeria and issues arising from embarking on PPP projects using various models. The theoretical framework has a subheading here, explaining why New Public Management theory best describes why Nigeria government embark on PPP projects. Summary and gap in the literature are also included in this chapter. Chapter Three discussed the background of the study area, the Tin can Island Port and the methodology used in the research such as study population, source of data, research instrument, method of data presentation and analysis and research challenges encountered during the study. Chapter Four is for Data Presentation and Analysis which gave a detailed analysis of the Measurement of Port Performance and Service Delivery at the TCIP, Discussion of Research Findings and Verification of Research Assumptions. Chapter Five discusses the summary of key findings, draws conclusions based on the results obtained from the various analyses and gave policy recommendations.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Introduction

This chapter gives a detailed review of concepts central to the subject under study. Also, it elucidates the relevance of ports to global, continental and regional economies as well as examined the failures and success of PPP adoption in several sectors of Nigeria's economy.

This section also examine case studies similar to the subject under study and justifies why there is a gap in other literature related to the topic which it has chosen to fill.

The chapter offers a fitting theoretical framework that guides the study showing its relevance and limitations in the Nigeria PPP case.

2.2 Conceptual Review

Concepts such as PPP and Concession which are key points to the research are explained. The study also analyzes the importance of port or the maritime to nation-states while giving insight into the impacts of its operations on the Nigerian economy, despite challenges and shortcomings.

Port Governance and Administration in Nigeria is compared to that of other countries with seaports to comprehend the change in the port governance model. Nigeria's adoption of PPP was put into focus explaining the relevance of PPP and concession model to the efficiency of the ports. Also, examples of projects executed using the PPP models in different sectors and states in Nigeria were analyzed to see shortcomings and challenges faced during the process.

2.2.1 Conceptual Perspectives

The research will be bland without clarification of certain concepts which are crucial to the thrust of the study, hence, we will be taking an in-depth analysis of these concepts – PPP and Concession.

2.2.1.1 Meaning and Models of PPP

Since PPP became an operative word within governance, public service and administration, it has been defined along the lines of funding, partnerships, sharing risk, providing essential service as well as enhancing development.

The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development defined PPP as:

an agreement between the government and one or more private partners (which may include the operators and the financiers) according to which the private partners deliver the service in such a manner that the service delivery objectives of the government are aligned with the profit objectives of the private partners and where the effectiveness of the alignment depends on a sufficient transfer of risk to the private partners (OECD, 2008, p. 17).

Also, the International Monetary Fund refer to PPPs as:

arrangements where the private sector supplies infrastructure assets and services that traditionally have been provided by the government. In addition to private execution and financing of public investment, PPPs have two other important characteristics: there is an emphasis on service provision, as well as investment, by the private investment; and significant risk is transferred from the government to the private sector. PPPs are involved in a wide range of social and economic infrastructure projects, but they are mainly used to build and operate hospitals, schools, prisons, roads, bridges and tunnels, light rail networks, air traffic control systems, and water and sanitation plants (IMF, 2004, p. 4; 2006, p. 1).

According to the Commission of the European Communities (2004, p. 3), the term PPP “refers to forms of co-operation between public authorities and the world of business which aim to ensure the funding, construction, renovation, management and maintenance of an infrastructure for the provision of a service.”

The Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission (ICRC) asserts that public-private partnership describes a government service or private business venture which is funded and operated through a partnership between a government and one or more private sector companies (ICRC PPP Manual, 2017, p. 7).

As per the National Policy on Public-Private Partnership of the Federal Government of Nigeria, a PPP is defined as a contract, whereby the private sector is engaged by the public sector to manage some public services, and to design, build, finance and operate some infrastructure to enhance efficiency, broaden access, and improve the quality of public services. The role of the public sector is to plan and structure projects, while the private sector directly implements the projects (ICRC PPP Manual, 2017, p. 7).

Since 1980, the UK government adopted PPP as a preferred method of economic regeneration and it's been used to deliver public projects across sectors such as education, healthcare, transport, public buildings, water and waste management, defense and IT facilities (Akintoye, 2009). Also, PPP adoption in the USA dated back to the 1950s and 1960s where it was used by government to strengthen the inner-city infrastructure. In more recent years, the USA has increased its interest in PPP to deliver public services, especially at the county and municipal levels. PPP application in the USA has moved from its historical application in solid waste disposal, building repair, street construction, vehicle repair and services towards public infrastructure provision like schools, inner-city redevelopment, car parks, administrative building, public plazas, and housing units (Li & Akintoye, 2003).

According to OECD (2008), several emerging market economies like Brazil, Chile, China and South Africa employ the use of PPP in public services delivery, though not without hitches in some of these countries. Leigland and Butterfield (2006) stated that Private participation in infrastructure development has been low in Africa since 1991 except in the telecommunication sector. Africa ranked lowest in private finance of infrastructure in the developing countries

with US\$39.4 billion investment in infrastructure projects in the year 1990–2004 far below Latin America with US\$391 billion and East Asia with US\$199 billion. South Africa had 50% of Africa’s share of the investment at US\$19 billion and Nigeria taking 14% in the 15 years (Abiodun, 2012).

The general practice in most African countries is to request for grants and aid from developed countries to finance infrastructure or even go-ahead to seek loans from global financial institutions to execute projects which put the country in a financial quagmire if the project does not have Value for Money (VfM) and also increase the debt profile of the country. Hence, the inception of PPP has opened a new way for these developing countries to ensure that projects are executed in such a way that it also opens coffers for additional funding for the country, thereby ensuring the government is not indebted to any foreign country or institution.

Grimsey and Lewis (2004), Niger State POG-PPP (2007), United Nations (2008), World Bank (2009) and Ugwu (2012) have simplified the types and models of PPP to include the following – Build Operate Transfer (BOT); Build Operate Train Transfer (BOTT); Build Own Operate Transfer (BOOT); Lease Develop Operate (LDO); Design Build Operate (DBO); Design Build Maintain (DBM); Build Transfer Operate (BTO); Buy Build Operate (BBO); Design Build Finance Operate (DBFO); Design Build Finance Transfer (DBFT); Build Own Operate (BOO); Rehabilitate, Operate and Transfer (ROT); Rehabilitate, Lease or Rent, and Transfer (RLT); Build, Rehabilitate, Operate, and Transfer (BROT); Concession Model (CM); Turn Key (TK); Contract Services (CS); Landlord Tenancy (LLT); Joint Venture (JV); Partnership Investment (PI); Policy Partnership (PP); Partnership Companies (PC); and Sales of Business by Flotation (SB).

However, the models of PPP in the table below have been categorized using contractual agreements between the parties involved such as the objective of the government, transferring investment risk, maintaining service control or improving the quality of service.

Table 2.2.1.2: Different Types of PPP Delivery Models

Nature of Contract (Duration)	Characteristics				Nature of service and Payment to contractor
	Asset Ownership	Operation & Management	Capital Investment	Commercial Risk	
Service Contract (1-3 years)	Public	Public & Private	Public	Public	A definitive, often technical type of service, the fee paid by the government for service
Management Contract (3-8 years)	Public	Private	Public	Public	Manage the operation of government service; the fee paid by the government for service and a performance-based incentive
Lease Contract (5-10 years)	Public	Private	Public	Private	Manage, operate, repair and maintain a public service to specified standards and outputs. All revenues, fees or charges are recovered from consumers or the users of the service; the service provider pays the government rent for the facility.
Concession Contract (25-30 years)	Public	Private	Private	Private	Manage, operate, repair, maintain and invest in public service infrastructure to specified standards and outputs. All revenues are sourced from consumers for the provision of the service; the service provider pays a Concession fee to the government and may assume existing debt.
BOT/BOO/ Others (15-25 years)	Private & Public	Private	Private	Private	Construct and operate, to specified standards and outputs, the facilities necessary to provide the service. The Government mostly pays the service provider on a unit basis.

Source: ICRC PPP Manual (2017)

The distinction between a BOT-type of arrangement and a Concession is that a Concession generally involves extensions to and operation of existing systems, whereas a BOT generally involves large “Green Field” investments requiring substantial outside finance, for both equity

and debt. However, in practice, a Concession contract may include the development of major new components as well as extensions to existing systems, and BOTs sometimes involve the expansion of existing facilities (ICRC PPP Manual, 2017).

2.2.1.2 Meaning of Concession and its relevance to PPP

Concession as defined by the Oxford English Dictionary (2019), refers to the action of conceding or granting something to someone or a business concern.

In commerce terms, concession means granting of exclusive privileges (such as the right to be the only seller of a good or service) by a government authority or by the owner of a singular property (such as an airport, amusement park, hotel) to a grantee or concessionaire, who pays rent or a certain percentage of the sales or earnings to the grantor (Business Dictionary, 2020).

Negotiation terms refer to concession as yielding a position, privilege or right, by a party to induce another party to respond similarly by yielding an equivalent position, right or privilege (Business Dictionary, 2020).

In development terms, concession simply refers to a kind of partnership between the public sector and a (usually) private company that has shown its added value in a specific area, for example, developing infrastructure or providing essential services.

According to the Asian Development Bank (ADB, 2008), concession makes the private sector operator (concessionaire) responsible for the full delivery of services in a specified area, including operation, maintenance, collection, management, and construction and rehabilitation of the system. The operator is responsible for all capital investment while the public sector is responsible for establishing performance standards and ensuring that the concessionaire meets them. Although the private sector operator is responsible for providing the assets, such assets may or may not be publicly owned during the concession period (ICRC PPP Manual, 2017).

Concessionaires either get paid by the public sector through budgetary allocation or generates its revenue through tariffs collected directly from the system users. The tariff is typically established by the Concession agreement or contract, which also includes provisions on how it may be changed over time.

In certain cases, the government may choose to provide financing support to help the Concessionaire fund its capital expenditures but the concessionaire is responsible for any capital investments required to build, upgrade, or expand the system, and for financing those investments out of its resources and from the tariffs paid by the system users, not to forget, the Concessionaire is also responsible for arranging the working capital.

A Concession contract is typically valid for 25–30 years so that the operator has sufficient time to recover the capital invested and earn an appropriate return over the life of the Concession. The public authority may contribute to the capital investment cost, if necessary. This can be an investment or subsidy (Viability Gap Financing) made to achieve the commercial viability of the project. Alternatively, the government can be compensated for its contribution by receiving a commensurate part of the tariff collected (ICRC PPP Manual, 2017).

The federal government of Nigeria enhanced PPP by putting up legislation that supports all PPP contracts to follow the concession model and establishing a commission like the ICRC to regulate all PPPs in Nigeria and act as the official project director.

2.2.2 The Importance of Ports to Nation-States

Oceans have always been an alien realm for humans but we have learned how to live on it, as ancient civilization and the progression of science, showed us the importance of having coastal areas. Ancient merchants used boats and ships to go on voyages where cities and continents were discovered, including Africa. During the journey on the sea, the phenomenon of tides,

wind and waves made sailors find sheltered areas for docking the boats and ships, which was how harbor areas came about before they metamorphosed into port areas.

A port is a location on a coast or shore containing one or more harbors where ships can dock and transfer people or cargo to or from land. Port locations are selected to optimize access to land and navigable water, for commercial demand, and shelter from wind and waves (Dwarakisha & Salim, 2015). There are natural port areas and artificial port areas.

Since time immemorial, ports have played an immense role in trade, commerce and politics. Empires became richer by trade and stronger by conquest, typical examples of these empires as explained by De Graauw (2014) were Rome and its four ports (Portus Tiberinus, Portus Claudius, Portus Trajanus and Ostia); Athens and its 4 ports (Kantharos, Munychia, Zea and Phaleron); Alexandria and its 2 maritime ports (Portus Magnus and Eunostos).

Ports are one of the major components of the general transport sector and it is linked to the expanding world economy. It has become a means of integration into the global economic system with countries boasting of their vibrant maritime sector.

The maritime sector encompasses a wide range of services, the transportation of goods and passengers being the primary one. Other related services included in this sector are various port services such as pilotage, towing and tug assistance, emergency repairs, anchorage berth and berthing services, etc. and auxiliary or supporting services such as storage and warehousing, maritime cargo handling services, customs clearance services, etc. (Dwarakisha & Salim, 2015).

Many world countries have encountered economic development and growth through their maritime sector. The countries that made it to the World Shipping Council's latest ranking of top 50 World's Busiest Port are China, Singapore, United Arab Emirate (Dubai), Malaysia, USA, Germany, Thailand, Hong Kong, Japan, Greece, Belgium, India, etc., the list has some

of the fastest-growing economies in the world and port operations have a significant contribution to their GDP.

Currently, there are 835 seaports in the world and over ninety percent of the world's trade moves through these inland ports, buttressing the significance of ports to nation-states.

China's maritime economy grew from \$21.2 billion in 2002 to \$210 billion in 2017 and the second-largest maritime industry in 2017 was maritime transport (mostly, shipping), contributing \$88 billion to the industry (To & Lee, 2018) and all the ports in the country are among the top 50 busiest container port in the world (World Shipping Council, WSC 2019).

According to a report by Martin Associates, the Ports and Shipping Industry in the US is responsible for 26% (45.4 trillion) of its \$20.5 trillion GDP in 2018 and created over 7 million jobs between 2014 and 2018 (Ronan, 2019) with two of its ports being among the top 50 busiest in the world. The Centre for Economic and Business Research (CEBR, 2017) estimated that the ports industry of the UK directly contributed £22.6 billion in business turnover, £7.6 billion in Gross Value Added (GVA) and 101,000 jobs for UK employees in 2016 while also handling over 95% of all the country's trade.

In 2017, the sea transport industry contributed seven percent of Singapore's \$323.9 billion GDP and it has one of the busiest ports in the world. Dubai's Jebel Ali Port is the tenth busiest port in the world and it contributed 33.4 percent to the city's \$111.9 billion GDP in 2017 and makes up over ten percent of the United Arab Emirates' \$384 billion GDP for the same year (Hellenic Shipping News, 2019).

The maritime and port industry contributed \$3.6 billion to Hong Kong's GDP in 2016, port and related accounted for 51%, shipping sector contributed 35% and maritime business activities had 14% (Transport and Housing Bureau, 2018).

Also, ports have been known to be one of the job creation sectors in the economy considering the activities involved in loading and offloading of cargoes, logistics and other services. In the US, the maritime sector created seven million jobs within four years, same can be said of the maritime sector in China which has four vibrant subsectors. The ports in the UK, Germany, India, and Singapore also create a hundred thousand job opportunities. Hundreds and thousands of jobs have been created through Africa's maritime sector.

In the African continent, there are over 100 port facilities cutting across over 38 countries, hence, the significance of port cannot be underestimated as it contributes more to the economies of countries like South Africa, Kenya, Tanzania, Ghana, Nigeria, Togo, Djibouti, Ivory Coast, which has the busiest and largest ports in the continent.

As of 2015, Ocean Economy in South Africa has contributed \$6.3 billion to the country's \$313 billion GDP and it has two of the busiest ports in Africa (South Africa's Ocean Economy, SAOE 2016) while in Tanzania's Port of Dar es Salaam, the cargoes handled at the port in 2012 was valued at \$15 billion.

Nigeria has the busiest port in West Africa, the Lagos ports (comprises of Apapa port and Tin Can Island Port) which contribute tremendously to the economy of the country, alongside five other port complexes. The country does not have a refinery, so petroleum products are exported to countries where they will be refined from these port areas and they come back to the country via the seaport, especially the Lagos port. Although the maritime sector in Nigeria is not captured in the nation's GDP, its influence on the growth of the country's economy is quite immense as over ninety percent of what Nigerians consume come in through the seaport which shows how invaluable the ports are to Nigeria's economy or why the government is striving to make it more viable.

2.2.3 Importance of Ports to the Nigerian Economy

In 2018, the Nigeria Customs Services (NCS) generated ₦1.2 trillion in revenue, the bulk of which came from import duties, the following year, it generated ₦1.002 trillion within nine months (January – September 2019) and the large chunk of the revenue came from the Apapa Area Command of the NCS (Nwagbara, 2019) where the Lagos ports are located. This shows that the maritime sector in the country has a tremendous impact on the economy and GDP of the country.

Unarguably, the Nigerian economy is driven by oil and gas exploration, production and sales but other major contributors are international cargo trade, customs duties, direct taxes and others (Ekpo, 2012). The existence of natural port areas in Nigeria made shipping central to the country's maritime sector due to its numerous revenue sources that still end up in government coffers such as fees for the registration of ships and their mortgages, registration of shipping companies, corporate taxes paid by shipping companies, ports charges and tariff paid to the NPA for the use of its facilities for vessels or ships which berth at Nigerian ports, fees for licensing paid by clearing and forwarding agents or freight forwarders, customs and excise duties paid to Nigeria Customs, the rent and throughput charges being paid by terminal operators to NPA.

Nigerian ports make international trade possible and provides job opportunities to its populace, it could be said that the maritime sector is one of the largest employers of labour in the country from Nigeria Customs Services (NCS), Nigeria Immigration Service (NIS), Port Police, Nigerian Navy, National Drugs Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA), Standard Organisation of Nigeria (SON), Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA), National Food and Drug Administration (NAFDAC), Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA), Nigerian Shippers Council (NSC), Nigeria Maritime Administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA), National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA), and others. It

would also be worthy to note that the revenue generated by these government agencies is some of the revenue sources for the country's annual budget.

Also, the available jobs in the maritime industry have a multiplier effect on the development of other economic activities like freight forwarding, dock working, stevedoring operations, towage, pilotage, warehousing, marine insurance, banking, bonded warehousing and cargo handling which also affect Nigeria's economic position (Igbokwe, 2001).

A study of port operations on Nigeria's economy conducted by Onyema, Obinna, Emenyonu and Emeghara (2015) concluded that the economy is dependent on crude oil and agricultural produce export to earn a foreign income whereas industries are dependent on the importation of materials needed for their consumption or production activities, therefore, stagnation in port operations will have dire economic consequences on the economic growth of the nation.

Although, there is no simplified data that shows the total contribution of the port sector to Nigeria's economy, the linkages and influence it has on its growth and development cannot be underestimated. The port sector also brings business into the country as landlocked nations like Chad and Niger use the Nigerian ports or other West African port areas as a point of delivery for their cargoes, this contributes to foreign exchange earnings.

The NPA has a monthly publication titled 'Shipping Position' which gives update on how vessels and ships arrive at the port laden with products such as petrol, containers of various merchandise, general cargo, bulk sugar, bulk wheat, frozen fish, bulk salt, steel products, cars, vehicles, machines, etc. This shows how invaluable the Nigerian ports have become to the daily activities of Nigeria's economic activities as well as its growth and development.

2.2.4 Port Governance and Administration in other countries

The governance, administration and ownership of ports are rich in experience transcending centuries, major civilizations, wars, trade relations and continued adaptation to changing world systems. Alderton (2005) provided a traditional classification of port ownership as; state ports, autonomous ports, municipal ports and private ports, through the years, the ownership status of the port has mutated into governance and administration models which the World Bank's Port Reform ToolKit has outlined into four – the Public Service port, the Tool port, the Landlord port and the Private Service port (World Bank, 2007).

The models differ in terms of whether services are provided by the public sector, the private sector or mixed ownership providers, their orientation (local, regional or global), the ownership of superstructure and who provides dock labour and management in which Baird (1997) identified as regulatory function, landowner function and operator function. Below is a table that further explains port governance and administration.

Table 2.2.4: Types of Port Governance Model

Type	Infrastructure	Superstructure	Workforce	Regulation
Landlord Port	Public	Private	Private	Public
Tool Port	Public	Public (Private)	Private (Public)	Public/Private
Public Service Port	Public	Public	Public	Public
Private Service Port	Private	Private	Private	Private/Public

Source: Bichou (2009)

According to the table above, the port (public or private) owns, maintains and develops both infrastructure and superstructure, operates all handling equipment, and performs on its own all other commercial port functions. Both landlord and tool ports own and develop their infrastructure, which is leased to the private sector, in this case, there is the national port authority that serves as a regulator. However, while the superstructure is owned and operated by private operators in the landlord model, the tool port still owns the superstructure but may

lease it for operational purposes to private companies (COMCEC Report, 2015). This distinction is not always obvious in that some ports may restrict superstructure assets to cargo handling equipment, while others extend them to storage, warehousing and logistics facilities. Even where a landlord structure is in place; the extent of the private sector involvement in port development, operations, and/or service provision can vary widely across port facilities.

In the United States, the maritime industry despite its numerous port areas does not have a national port authority, rather authority is diffused throughout all three levels of government – federal, state and local, this stems from the federal character of the U.S. Constitution, which reserves certain powers for the national government and others strictly for the states (Sherman, 2012). The US Ports are heavily subsidized by the government but its operations, labour and other superstructures are being handled by private enterprises, likened to practicing Private Service Model or Tool Port Model. The arrangement seems to be a working partnership considering that the seaport is one of the most viable in the world.

In the case of the UK, changes in the governance of ports in the UK began with the sale of shares in Associated British Ports on the London Stock Exchange in 1983, followed by the 1991 Ports Act, the governance of UK ports was fully incorporated into private sector model. This arrangement may have been faulted on many levels as the government abandoned its regulatory function but UK ports remain viable, Port of Felixstowe is one of the busiest ports in the world (WSC, 2019).

Canadian Ports moved from Public Service model to Landlord Model around 1999 with the government acting as landlord and performing other regulatory function but operations have either handed over to regional, local or private investors (Brooks, 2004), Hong Kong, Djibouti, Iran, Malaysia, Nigeria, Saudi Arabia, Singapore, practice the Landlord model for port governance and administration (COMCEC Report, 2015) and their port sectors seem to be booming.

In China, Egypt, the Gambia, Indonesia, Iraq, Jordan, Kuwait, Morocco, Oman, Qatar, Turkey, among others, the Public Service model is being used for port governance and administration.

Most of the port facilities in Africa were formerly using Public Service Model but most of them have adopted either the Landlord model or Tool Port model to finance port infrastructure, tackle inadequacies, lukewarm service delivery and boost investment in the maritime sector.

Data shows that some of the most viable ports in the world have either transferred to Private Service Model or Landlord port model or Tool port model.

2.2.5 Port Governance and Service Delivery in Nigeria

The first seaports in Nigeria were found in Warri and Benin between 1471 and 1472 during the Portuguese exploration of the shores of the Bights of Benin and Biafra. The seaports facilitated trade in pepper, ivory and slaves between peoples of Nigeria and foreigners. The first Portuguese trade mission under D'Aveiro visited Benin in 1486. The foremost ports in Nigeria were located at Gwato in the Benin kingdom and Forcados in the Itsekiri kingdom (Akinwale & Aremo, 2010). Before the coming of the Europeans there was no need for an extensive system of water transport, as these peoples looked to interior tributary areas, and not coastward. The interior ports declined in the eighteenth century as a result of the general neglect of the western Delta by Europeans, which appears to have been a function of the small volume of trade. The well-organized military state of Benin had collapsed by the end of the seventeenth century, and only limited traffic in slaves and ivory was available (Ogundana, 1972).

Following the collapse of the Benin kingdom, the volume of trade became high at the Bight of Biafra and its environs including Brass, Akassa, Calabar, Bonny and Opobo. Subsequently, the British gained control of seaports in Nigeria in the 1860s through the establishment of seaports in Lagos and Akassa (the base of the Royal Niger Company) followed by the promulgation of the Niger Coast Protectorate in 1890.

The center of ports operation in Nigeria was shifted to Apapa in the 1920s, the decision to develop Apapa Port was taken in 1913 and construction of the first four deep-water berths of 548.64metres long at Apapa began in 1921. Similarly, Port Harcourt Port was opened to shipping in 1913. Four berths of 1,920 feet long were developed at the Port Harcourt Port in 1927, and following a report by the Port Harcourt Port Advisory Board, the sum of four million pounds was provided for the first major extension work of the Port Harcourt Port in 1954. The NPA was established in April 1955 to harness the success of the ports industry for the development of Nigerian society. The NPA's development strategy was harmonized with the first National Development Plan (1962-1968) which resulted in the improvement of port facilities in Lagos and Port Harcourt with an expenditure of 45 million naira. However, Nigerian ports suffered setbacks during the civil war (1967-1970) when Port Harcourt port was closed to foreign traffic, while Lagos port became the only available port serving the country's maritime transportation needs. The Federal Government of Nigeria enacted a special decree to empower the NPA to acquire the private ports in eastern Nigeria such as the Warri Port owned by Holts Transport, the Burutu Port owned by the UAC and the Calabar Port jointly owned by five operators (Akinwale & Aremo, 2010).

Congestion of Nigerian ports reached an unprecedented level in the aftermath of the civil war. Also, existing roads were inadequate to cope with the expeditious evacuation of cargoes and the situation was aggravated by an increase in the volume of importation in the 1970s. The congestion resulted in the imposition of surcharges while ships had to wait for an average of 180 days before they could berth and by 1975, the average waiting time of ships in Lagos Port was approximately 250 days. Hence, to release this tremendous pressure on the port system, the NPA embarked on some emergency measures including the emergency construction of a new port in the Lagos area (Tin Can Island), acquisition of equipment and attempts to increase productivity of berths (Shneerson, 1981).

However, a previously booming import business that kept the Nigerian Ports busy in the 1970s gradually scaled down in the 1980s as a result of economic recession. The Federal Government of Nigeria commercialised the NPA in 1992, thereby changing it to the Nigerian Ports Plc (NPP), which was reverted to its original name in October 1996. By 2000, Nigeria Ports had become a shadow of itself, in the move to improve service delivery and address the ineptitude and mismanagement in the maritime sector, Nigerian ports were integrated into the history of privatization in Nigeria through the reforms that led to the adoption of port concession.

World Bank (2017) outlined four port governance models namely the Public Service port, the Tool port, the Landlord port and the Private Service port, a further analysis of Nigerian ports showed how port operations have utilized these models since its inception.

Nigerian ports began operations in the pre-colonial era using the private service port as a model for port operations and administration, the multinational companies that had branches in Nigeria were used by the colonial masters in handling port business. Multinationals like Holt, UAC, amongst others ensured that the port was available for the transport of raw materials to the headquarters of their respective companies and processed, the same channel was used in bringing these finished goods into Nigeria for sales and distribution to colonial masters and Nigerians.

This arrangement made multinationals and the British government handle regulatory function, landowner function and operator function of the Nigerian ports but in the quest to indigenize port operations and administrations in Nigeria, the NPA was established in 1955 and mixed model (public service and private service port) became operational, as some multinationals were still involved in port governance. In the early 1970s, port operations had challenges due to the civil war but the post-civil war reform made sure that ports administration shifted fully to the public service port model. Since then, Nigerian ports were administered as public ports because of the crucial role ports play in the country's economic development and to protect

public safety and security but with the commercialisation of the ports in 1992 and the Port Act of 1999, the NPA adopted the tool port system of administration.

Before the concession, all the ports in Nigeria practiced the Tool port model, except Onne port that leaned towards the Landlord model (Pinwa, 1999). According to Nwanosike (2014), while the tool port model was in effect, the Federal Government through the NPA provided the port infrastructure and superstructure, as well as cargo handling equipment, such as quay cranes and forklifts, which are operated by port authority staff but cargo handling onboard vessels, aprons and quays are the responsibility of cargo handling companies contracted by shipping agents, or other entities licensed by the port authority.

As observed by the World Bank (2007), the sharing of responsibility between the port authorities and stevedoring companies created operational problems and inefficiency in the Tool port model. Although private firms play some role in cargo handling in this model, they are not obliged by agreement to bring in new investments. Thus, pre-concession Nigeria seaports were littered with a small number of private firms involved in cargo handling with a weak capital base and lacking innovation. It resulted in chronic underinvestment in the Nigerian port system. Therefore, the port system could no longer cope with the rapid global development in the shipping sector and regional competition from the Cotonou port in the Benin Republic as well as Lome in Togo, Tema port in Ghana and Douala port in Cameroun, due to infrastructural decay (Nwanosike, 2014).

To mitigate the general dissatisfaction with the Nigerian port system by stakeholders, a massive port reform was initiated from 2003-2005, which culminated in the adoption of the Landlord model of port administration and the handing over of terminal operations to the private sector in May 2006 (Nwanosike, 2014). The private operators were put in charge of cargo handling activities and expected to bring in the needed investment while the NPA handles pilotage, towage, warehousing, provision of infrastructure and other equipment.

2.3 The Adoption of PPP in Nigeria

El-Rufai (2003) stated that the Federal Government of Nigeria had a total of 590 public enterprises by May 1999 and the enterprises could not arrest the core problems of widespread poverty, growing inequality, and rising unemployment, which promote stagnation and retrogression of the economic life of an average Nigerian. Before then, several commission reports such as Adebo commission of 1969, Udoji commission of 1973, Onasode commission of 1981, Al-Hakim commission of 1984, amongst others have reported that public enterprises confront several problems such as defective capital structure, bureaucratic bottleneck, mismanagement, gross inefficiency and corruption. These problems facing the state-owned enterprises (SOEs) were first tackled with the call for privatization and led to the establishment of the Technical Committee on Privatization and Commercialization (TCPC) in 1988 but the policy actions taken during this period were unable to bring positive results. However, the Federal Government after the return to civil rule in May 1999 doubled up on its efforts on privatization and established the following institutional frameworks for privatization – the National Privatisation Act of 1999, the National Council on Privatization (NCP) and the Bureau for Public Enterprises (BPE) [Akinwale & Aremo, 2010].

The state of infrastructure facilities in Nigeria when the country returned to civilian rule in May 1999 was desolate and underperforming and some of the recommendations put forward by the panel set up by the Obasanjo administration was to privatize public enterprise. Hence, the administration set the wheels of the National Privatization (Privatization and Commercialization) Act of 1999 into motion and privatized some public enterprises to boost its efficiency and one of the foremost projects is the concession of Nigerian ports, to reform port governance and operations in the country. The BPE was the government agency that handled the privatization and commercialization of public enterprise and it was extended through the setup of the NCP.

The federal government of Nigeria continued to promote privatization through the activities of the BPE, the NCP and also seeking technical assistance from global financial institutions like the World Bank which assisted the government in terms of research on enterprises that should be privatized to boost efficiency and access to private finance as well as creating avenues to legitimize PPP by helping to set up its framework, technical expertise, investors, amongst others. However, President Obasanjo gave his official approval to PPP when he signed the Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission (establishment, etc.) Act in 2005 encompassing an administrative, legal, and technical framework under which PPP is embarked on and executed but the commission and its governing board were inaugurated in November 2008 during the Late President Yar'adua's administration.

States have also adopted the PPP strategy in funding many of their huge infrastructural projects and sharing the risk with private investors, states like Lagos, Port Harcourt and Niger have enacted legislation to promote and regulate PPP. However, the Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission Act (ICRCA) does not apply to infrastructure projects undertaken by state governments where no federal asset or ministry is involved but its projects may be financed with the support of a guarantee by the federal government, because various agencies of the World Bank and some other global financial institutions work through the federal government. However, almost all the states in Nigeria have begun to use the PPP framework to finance infrastructure and bring investment to their doorstep. The World Bank Group (WBG) ranked Nigeria as one of the top four leading voices for PPP in 2017 (Premium Times, 2017).

The ICRC's enabling act mandates the commission to manage the complex arrangements that the PPP process entails, as well as build capacity within MDAs to handle such arrangements themselves within the scope of infrastructure PPP like Power Generation and Transmission/Distribution Networks; Roads and Bridges; Ports; Railways; Inland Container Depots and Logistics Hubs; Gas and Petroleum Infrastructure such as Storage Depots and

Distribution Pipelines; Water Supply, Treatment and Distribution Systems; Solid Waste Management; Educational Facilities (e.g. Schools, Universities); Urban Transport Systems; Housing; and Healthcare Facilities (ICRC, 2017) and all these projects cut across all the states in the country. In 2017, the agency launched the PPP Contracts Disclosure on its web portal, making Nigeria rank as one of the first countries in the world to embark on such a feat.

2.3.1 PPP in Nigerian States: A Case of Lagos and Niger states

Before the federal government adopted PPP to finance public infrastructure, Lagos state had already set the precedence of embarking on the first PPP project in Nigeria with the Lekki-Epe Expressway Toll Road aimed at providing sustainable solutions to challenges of heavy traffic congestion along Lekki Peninsula. The project commenced in 2000 but the 30 years concession agreement was signed in 2006 during the Tinubu administration.

The BOT contract agreement between the Lagos State Government and Lekki Concession Company Limited (LCC) for the rehabilitation and upgrade of the 50 kilometres expressway is adjudged to be one of the first private toll projects in Africa outside of South Africa. The road project won three major finance industry awards and the success recorded from it led to the award of the contract and management of toll collection for Lekki-Ikoyi Link Bridge to LCC.

However, the Lekki-Epe road project is trailed by controversy both in the court of law and outside it as LCC only built less than 10 kilometres of the road and tolled it to raise funds for its completion (Adedayo, 2016), toll tariff has been increased multiple times and the toll gateway usually causes multi-dimensional gridlock around the area. Nonetheless, the state continues to promote PPP projects in housing with the Lagos State Property Development Commission (LSDPC), commerce and industry through the Lagos State Employment Trust Fund (LSETF), waste management through PSP and VisionScape, market through the reconstruction of the Tejuosho market gutted by fire, transport, agriculture, etc.

Niger state was also another early bloomer in PPP projects in Nigeria. During the Aliyu administration, the state government targeted building 10,000 housing units to address the deficiency in the housing sector using the PPP option. The PPP framework allowed private concerns (developers) to raise funds for the construction of the housing units while the state government contributed land and basic infrastructure at the sites (The Nation, 2014). Several developers jumped on the mass housing delivery programme within Minna and other areas.

As of 2015, only the M. I. Wushishi Housing Estate has been completed and the 500 housing units occupied, however, reports showed that the construction had many defects such as the use of substandard building materials, abandonment of project and breach of Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) which caused the initial agreement of seven months for project completion to extend to two and a half years (Sayedi, Ringim & Ibrahim, 2016). Despite these challenges, the state made its mark as one of the pacesetters for PPP projects in Nigeria.

Moving forward, states across Nigeria has subscribed to the PPP mantra, to finance infrastructural projects as well as improve service delivery issues in public organizations.

2.3.2 Issues Arising from PPP and Concession in Nigeria: Example of Federal Projects

It would be appropriate to note that before the PPP model became official government policy in 2005, Federal Housing Authority (FHA) had adopted the PPP program in 2000 to build and complete 651 housing units in Gwarinpa II Estate Abuja. Also, other federal agencies used it to pilot developmental projects before PPP became an official public policy in Nigeria (U-Dominic; Ezeabasili; Okoro; Dim & Chikezie, 2015:72).

The underlying principle in Nigerian PPP transactions is that risks are allocated to the party best able to manage them while remuneration of the private party in a PPP transaction depends on the terms of the contract. Private investors or bidders are required to submit their proposal as a technical offer and a financial offer and only financial offers from bidders who pass the

technical stage (cut-off is usually 70 percent) are opened while a scoring system that combines the technical score with the financial offer is used to select the preferred bidder (Ollor, Etomi & Oyedeji, 2017).

PPPs in Nigeria have been structured in such a manner that the private party is paid directly from user fees, which is the payment mechanism often used in PPP road projects such as toll roads as seen in the Lekki-Epe Expressway project. The private party may also be paid directly from the government authority either in the form of availability payments (the government pays when services above the specified quality standards are delivered by the private party), minimum revenue guarantees (where the government compensates the private party if the actual revenues from the users fall short of the guaranteed amount) or subsidized payments.

It would not be an exaggeration to surmise that all of the pioneer PPP projects have been controversial and not quite short of scandals. The port concession was not handed over to the investors for over a year due to the industrial action engaged in by port and dock workers refuting the over 71% decrease in the port workforce which warranted the interference of International Labour Organization (ILO) and costing the federal government about US\$ 400 million (Nwanosike, 2014; Adedayo, 2016).

Also, concessions in the aviation industry, which either never saw the light of the day, or which were completed amidst controversy like the one between the Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria (FAAN) and Maevis Nigeria Limited to shore up the authority's revenue base through the Airport Operations Management System (AOMS) was a classic case of a concession gone awry as FAAN staff accused the concessionaire of many wrongdoings before terminating the contract citing breach of agreements. Maevis took the case to court and the judge ruled in its favour. Not only that, the original contract for Bi-Courtney Aviation Services Ltd. to build and manage Murtala Muhammed Airport 2 (MMA 2) was signed in 2003 followed by a supplementary agreement increasing the construction period from 18 to 33 months and in

February 2007, an addendum agreement was further signed to increase the concession period to 36 years from the original 12 years. FAAN also allowed some domestic airlines to operate local flights from the General Aviation Terminal (GAT) contrary to its agreement with Bi-Courtney, thereby undercutting the concessioner's revenue stream which the concessionaire took to court and was ruled that the original agreement should be followed (International Centre for Investigative Reporting, ICIR 2012), financial problem and other issues have trailed the project.

According to ICIR, the failure of the PPP project in Nigeria was also repeated in manifolds when the government decided to concession Lagos/Ibadan expressway to Bi Courtney Highway Services Limited (a subsidiary of Bi-Courtney Limited) in 2009. The agreement was for Bi Courtney to design, build, operate and transfer ownership of the road but it was riddled with controversies like choice of concessionaire, technical, legal and financial issues and the newly inaugurated ICRC did a report in which it advised the government not to go ahead with the deal and suggested that a detailed condition survey needed to be done to ascertain the cost of the project but was not heeded before the agreement was signed. Hence, the project was smeared by many challenges and controversies before President Jonathan's administration cancelled the contract in 2012.

The Port concession in Nigeria still has issues trailing it, after thirteen years of transferring ownership to private terminals. The extension of the contract for Five Star Logistics Limited and Josepdam Port Services Limited (at the TCIP) by five years was due to the issues they had with the former occupants of the terminals which affected their operations for a while. Also, reconstruction of access roads to the Lagos port has been a source of worry considering the slow movement of the project which was awarded to Dangote Group by the federal government as well as the constant call for decongestion of port roads which has had little to no success.

In conclusion, the PPP projects embarked on in Nigeria have had their issues but it is still the best alternative to finance public infrastructure, however, the federal government needs to allow the ICRC to perform the function it is established and given the mandate to carry out.

2.4 Empirical Review

The research conducted an empirical review of literature relating to PPP, port concession and Nigerian port, below is a detailed summary of the empirical gaps in these earlier studies and how this new study will be plugging the discovered loopholes.

Ugwu's (2012) dissertation on the viability of PPP as an option for infrastructural development in Nigeria using Enugu state between 2007 and 2012 as a case study exalted the advantages of engaging in PPP in the state and Nigeria, however, the quantitative research obtained its data through a close-ended questionnaire and purposively chose respondents from only people who knew what PPP means. The study used a research design where sample size and data collection focused only on those who understood what PPP means, it also examined only successful projects and neglected failed ones, leading to generalized assumptions that PPP is viable for infrastructural development in Enugu state and Nigeria.

This new study examined the viability of only one subsector of the transport sector using multiple data collection such as annual report, questionnaire and interviews to analyze port operations before and after the adoption of PPP to determine PPP's viability in that sector only.

Abiodun's (2012) thesis examined the role of PPP in Highway Infrastructure Development and Sustainability in Nigeria using qualitative and quantitative methods of research. The research used the qualitative method to analyze official documents and questionnaires to conduct an in-depth analysis of the highway Performance Indicators and their Critical Success Factors under DBB and PPP methods (using case studies of highway projects completed and ongoing). The comparative analysis of the research findings showed that the DBB method used for highway

development in Nigeria generally results in cost and time overruns, low-quality road network occasioned by the lack of adequate public financing, poor road maintenance management system, suboptimal risk-sharing and inefficient procurement process. The findings also showed that PPP by way of its financial models, efficient procurement, operation and maintenance processes, technical and managerial capacities, as well as the bundling of design, construction and maintenance in a single contract package may produce timely, cost-effective, good quality and sustainable highway network in Nigeria.

Even though the research put PPP in the transport sector in Nigeria at the forefront, it still bundled many road projects into one before arriving at a generalized conclusion, however, this new study focused on the ports, the use of the PPP concession model and its impact on a single port complex, the TCIP.

Nwanosike's (2014) thesis evaluated Nigerian ports' post-concession performance using quantitative data that involves outputs and inputs related to the port's production function. The variables of the research were analyzed using non-parametric data envelopment analysis (DEA) to determine the efficiency of the ports and the Malmquist Productivity Index to determine the sources of productivity change. The results of the analysis suggested that the productive performance of the ports improved after the transfer of terminal operations to the private sector, though not in all the ports, thus indicating that the wholesale concession of the ports is not the best as some ports would have been better left under public ownership.

This study examined all the twenty-five ports concession in Nigeria which was what led to the conclusion but in this new research, only five which are under the TCIP using growth rate analysis for before and after concession.

Also, Nwanosike's study was corroborated by Onwuegbuchunam (2018), having studied all these ports by applying key performance indicator metrics and parameters of queuing model in

assessing the performance of the concessioned port terminals but this new study limited key performance indicator metrics to TCIP and its terminals and measured the growth rate of cargo throughput, container throughput, vehicular traffic and berth occupancy rate at the TCIP.

The Lagos Container Terminals Concession was used as a case study to examine PPP as an anchor for diversifying the Nigeria economy in a study conducted by Deloitte Nigeria (2017) and it verified that port concession has a positive influence on the economy of Nigeria and improved service delivery of the Nigerian ports, but this new study analyzed one of the ports, the TCIP and its performance on Nigeria's economy.

This new study will be building on Pinwa's (1999) dissertation which first examined the performance of the landlord port in Nigeria, using the Onne port as a case study. The dissertation used growth rate analysis to determine the viability of the Onne port before and after the adoption of the landlord port model. Hence, this new study analyzed port performance through the growth rate of the TCIP before and after its concession.

2.5 Summary and Gaps in Literature

As stated in the empirical review, similar research conducted on Nigerian ports and its concession examined: impact analysis used either qualitative or quantitative method of data collection, these are the gaps noted in the empirical review of similar literature. Also, there is a scarcity of research works that focuses on unilateral study of port complexes. This research focuses on determining the viability of the TCIP as a measure of service delivery in port performance, port users' patronage, cargo clearance procedure, revenue generation and infrastructural facilities.

2.6 Theoretical Framework

The New Public Management (NPM) Theory was adopted for this study. NPM posits that when embarking on a public service project, whether fully-funded by government or under a PPP arrangement, the use of market-based approach will curtail the pathologies of government bureaucracy while providing the public with essential services.

Some of the proponents of NPM theory include Wilenski (1988); Pollitt (1990); Hood (1991); Peters (1996); Klitgaard (1997); and Hope (2002). In the course of gathering materials on PPP, it was noted that many researchers who have written about it have used neoliberalism theory, agency theory, public-choice theory, transaction cost theory, new public management theory to substantiate their position on the adoption of PPP (Ugwu, 2012; Cole, 2012; Kariuki, 2014).

However, the NPM theory centers on the private finance of infrastructure, competition and implementing business and management strategies that would make the agreement between the government and private investors succeed. In various ways, NPM characteristics sets the institutional, legal and operational foundation for PPPs across the continent.

NPM theory was introduced to public sector organizations in the late 1970s and one of the most influential factors leading to its emergence has been the historical shift in state ideology since the late 1970s in advanced capitalist nations toward a neo-liberal framework, which rejects the welfare state, opposes a large public sector, doubts government capacity, blames public bureaucracy, believes in private sector superiority, and emphasizes market competition in service delivery (Haque, 2004). The transition to NPM has taken place in major Western countries, especially Australia, Canada, New Zealand, the UK, and the US, irrespective of the differences in their forms of government and political parties. However, as of early 1980s, the reform initiative championed by NPM has also been implemented as policies within countries like Canada, Denmark, Greece, France, Italy, Portugal, amongst others.

2.6.1 Assumptions of NPM Theory

NPM theory has been inspired by theoretical perspectives such as public-choice theory, management theory, classical public administration, neoclassical public administration, policy analysis, principal-agent theory, property-rights theory, the neo-Austrian school, transaction-cost economics, and New Public Administration (Gruening, 2001). Gruening's study of NPM revealed that the theory has been amassing its characteristics from other pioneer theories as far back as the 1920s with classical public administration.

The characteristics of NPM, simply put, basic assumptions includes budget cuts; privatization; contracting out; user charges; competition and freedom to manage; decentralization; the separation of provision and production; the separation of politics and administration; performance measurement and improved accounting; Strategic planning and changed management styles; and use of information technology (Gruening, 2021; Diefenbach, 2009).

Budget cuts is a major driver for the NPM stating that government usually suffers from money shortages which leads to budget cuts for capital projects. In situation when this happens as seen with the Nigerian ports, the best option for the government is to either *privatize* or use PPP arrangement in order to maximize resources. Also, *contracting out* the public service project to specialized managers who have comparative advantage in terms of finance, expertise or natural resources is a welcomed policy decision under NPM.

The NPM sees *competition* as a healthy path for service providers, in this case, investors or stakeholders providing a particular service should be more than one, for instance, there are many private terminals under contract to offer similar cargo handling services at the Nigerian ports but they have *freedom to manage* and deliver their well-defined roles within the port. NPM also believes that *user charges* should be attached to the services provided, citizens should be able to pay to enjoy efficient service for a public good.

Decentralization is important to NPM as it supports *the separation of provision and production* and *the separation of politics and administration*, which is clearly spelled out under the PPP arrangement that a particular party handles regulatory function while the other focuses on cargo handling services. The *performance measurement* under NPM is purported to be systematic, regular and comprehensive in capturing, measuring, monitoring and assessing organizational and service delivery performance using growth indicators.

Strategic planning using market-based approach is the core for NPM, in some cases, it is a good call to *change management styles* as it fosters faster decision-making processes, for Nigerian ports, this has been instrumental for overhauling the administrative system. Then, NPM posits that *use of information technology* is a pragmatic idea that can help to streamline activities and boost productivity.

2.6.2 Relevance and Limitations of the Theory

The NPM theory's relevance to the study begins from the moment when it posited that there will always be budget cuts when such arises, it should not stop the government from providing public infrastructure which can be realized by bringing in investors and specialized contractors through privatization and contracting out, respectively. PPP has made it normal for the government to accept project pitches from private investors to carry out certain projects on its behalf or in partnership. The port concession agreements signed between the government and private investors is either for control, management or operation of the port terminals for a specified period, which creates a positive shift in service delivery that will benefit the public.

The landlord model of port governance model was used to transfers basic port infrastructure and services to private companies to manage and provide cargo-handling services. At the TCIP, this arrangement is between the government and five private terminal operators instilling competition among the investors while the government promotes value for money (VfM)

projects. These PPP arrangement is for a period of twenty to thirty years while the investors have freedom to build new facilities, upgrade the equipment and use the terminals to conduct maritime business and operations within the specified period. Also, these investors have carte blanche to use strategies that will make them get back the money invested in the venture by increasing user charges paid by end users.

NPM promotes decentralization which is important for the landlord model which clearly states that the NPA will provide port infrastructure and superstructure including cargo handling equipment such as quay cranes and forklifts, which are operated by port authority staff but cargo handling onboard vessels, aprons and quays are the responsibility of private terminal operators. Also, the terminal operators will be paying annual rent to NPA throughout the duration of the concession agreement while the port authority performs regulates functions.

NPM buttresses its relevance to PPP as it supports strategic planning and change in management style to promote efficiency. For instance, the concession of the port complex and changing management style has brought innovation to Nigeria's maritime sector, the NPA and private terminals have automated port operations and collapsed their services to reduce red-tape in cargo handling services. Hence, NPM gives room for a win-win situation whereas the government shifts financial burden to investors, investors make money from developing the infrastructure and the end-users get better service delivery.

Though NPM is a mix of values that fits the current situation and solve current administrative problems for government and investors but the solutions it provides may still not be able to curtail hereditary problems within certain sectors. In some cases, this has proven to be true as there is still obvious issues of congestion at the Lagos ports after the concession of the terminals and changing management style.

In terms of limitations, the NPM theory has been faulted for always promoting politicization of projects being executed under PPP as it promotes project that has huge investment returns for the investors and increases government revenue like the concession of these ports with the NPA collecting huge rent on behalf of the federal government on yearly basis.

Also, the theory still promotes excessive bureaucracy when executing PPP projects as seen in some projects that take years before moving onto the next stage of the procurement process or even implementation since the bureaucrats have failed to prioritize these projects, leaving it to deteriorate further like the concession of Kirikiri Lighter Terminal (KLT) which went on for years before it was suddenly cancelled.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter gives a detailed description of the study area, the TCIP, methodology used in the research such as study population, source of data, research instrument, method of data presentation and analysis as well as research challenges encountered during the study.

3.2 Background of the Study Area

The idea for the expansion of port operations in Nigeria became a necessity when the country experienced increased economic activities due to high influx of imports and exports during the oil boom in 1975 coupled with the post-civil war reconstruction. The period was characterized by the high volume of imports and export that resulted in serious port congestion in which the resultant effect created a situation where it became necessary for the government to initiate an actual means of decongesting the Port; by constructing a new Port on Tin Can Island. In 1976, the construction of the new Port started and was commissioned on 14th October 1977 and christened Tin Can Island Port (TCIP), with the capacity of handling 10-16 vessels at a time with the main port complex occupying a total area of 73 hectares. Tin Can Island Port is located in the North West area of Lagos Port Complex and has a bearing of Latitude 62°N Longitude 30° 23E (Nigeria Port Authority, NPA 2017).

Tin Can Island Port Complex is an amalgam of what used to be Roll-On-Roll-Off (RoRo) and Tin Can Island Ports. This merger came with the concession of the terminals to five terminal operators Josepdam Ports Services Limited (JPS), Tin Can Island Container Terminal Limited (TICT), Ports and Cargo Handling Services Limited (SIFAX Group), Five Star Logistics Limited (FSL), and Port and Terminal Multiservices Limited (PTML) with different

concession agreements in May 2006 after NPA adopted the Landlord model for port governance.

Table 3.2: Private Terminal Operators at the Tin Can Island Port Complex

Terminal	Operators	Type of cargo	Depth (m)
Terminal A	Josepdam Port Services Ltd.	Bulk	13.2
Terminal B	TICT Container Ltd.	Containers	13.3
Terminal C	Ports & Cargo Handling Services	Multipurpose	13.3
Terminal D	Five Star Logistics	Ro-Ro	12.9
Terminal E	Port & Terminal Multiservices Ltd.	Multipurpose	11.3

Source: NPA (2017)

Private terminal operators took over on the 10th of May, 2006 for Terminal A, C and D (Josepdam Ports Services Limited, Ports and Cargo Handling Services Limited and Five Star Logistics Limited respectively), Terminal B (Tin Can Island Container Terminal Limited) was handed over on the 1st of June, 2006 while Port and Terminal Multiservices Limited (PTML), which is the only BOT commenced operation in September, 2006 (NPA, 2017).

Ships and vessels coming in from about 100 countries of the world berth at the TCIP, as it engages in the maritime business of handling diversified cargoes like general cargoes (cars, lorries, buses, other vehicles, chemical preparations, fertilizers, frozen fish, iron and steel plates, steel billet, tallow oil, etc.), dry bulk cargoes (crude salt, fertilizers, grains/wheat, sugar, soya beans, palm kernel, malt and barley, bitumen and tar products, paper reels, hardboard, etc.), liquid bulk cargoes (chemical preparations, drilling fluid, spirits, liquors, wines, refined petroleum, refined tallow oil, etc.), box-containerized cargoes, RoRo services (TCIPC Annual Report, 2017), project cargo (for heavy-duty construction equipment, heavy lifts, tanks, boats, helicopters, etc.), premium container services.

The port terminals handle vessels ranging from 100m – 260m; Pilotage at the port runs 24-hour service with a positive track record of the quick turnaround time of vessels; Water supply has

a 250m well sunk available to vessels at berth and bunkering of vessels are undertaken by reputable oil companies; Regular sea patrol of all anchorage, jetties and fairway buoys with the able assistance of the Marine Police and the Nigerian Navy; and Operations are also being monitored by the Closed Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras (NPA, 2017).

3.3 Research Design

To make the study exploratory and descriptive, the mixed-method research design was used, relying on quantitative and qualitative research methods.

Tin Can Island Port is the research case study and instruments such as questionnaires were administered to Port users (Truck drivers, Clearing and Forwarding Agents, Shipping company staff) while interviews were conducted with Port personnel (Nigeria Customs staff at TCIP, NPA TCIP staff, Private Terminal Operators' Staff). The justification for choosing these categories of people as port users are based on the fact that they patronize TCIP on a day-to-day basis and have an idea of the services offered and the satisfaction derivative from the services rendered at the terminals. Also, the justification for pooling from this port personnel is that they are the ones who make and mar port operations TCIP and are also part of the new port administration, following the use of the landlord model of port governance.

Also, data was sourced from the TCIP Annual reports for years 2003, 2007 to 2017 and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) Reports on Port statistics 2012 to 2017 and aggregated to measure port performance.

3.3.1 Population of the Study

The study population is pulled from the case study used, the TCIP, which includes both port users and personnel.

According to the NBS (2017), the annual passenger traffic at Nigerian ports as of 2016 was 12,861, this represents the population of port users that patronize TCIP on a day-to-day basis. These 12,861 daily port users which includes truck drivers, clearing and forwarding agents, shipping company staff are eligible to become part of the respondents for the study.

Also, the data gotten from the TCIPC Annual Report for 2017 revealed that it had 284 officers and 108 staff, totaling up to 392 personnel at the NPA TCIP Complex. This represents the population of port personnel for the study.

3.3.2 Sample Size

The sample size for port users was ascertained using Krecjie and Morgan (1970) sample size selection formula stated as:

$$S = \frac{X^2NP (1 - P)}{D^2 (N - 1) + X^2P (1 - P)}$$

Where S is the required sample size; X^2 is the table value of chi-square for 1 degree of freedom at the desired confidence level (3.841); N is the population size; P is the population proportion which assumed to be 0.50 since it would provide the maximum sample size; D is the degree of accuracy expressed as a proportion (0.05).

According to Krecjie and Morgan (1970), as the population increases, the sample size increases at a diminishing rate and remains relatively constant at slightly more than 380 cases, if the population exceeds 50,000.

According to NBS (2017), the annual port passenger traffic was pegged at 12,861, this was substituted in the formula above, and the result showed that a sample size of three hundred and seventy (370) port users was required as respondents for the study.

However, the simple random probability sampling method was used to select these respondents from the clearing agents, truck drivers, and shipping company staff that uses the TCIP.

The non-probability sampling technique were adopted in interviewing port personnel, however, the researcher used purposive sampling to narrow down interviewees from the 108 staff at the TCIP. Using a sample size calculator, with a confidence level of 95%, an interval of 30 and a population of 108 staff pegged the sample size for interviewees as ten (10).

During fieldwork, only eight (8) personnel granted the research an interview, they are Personal Assistant to the Port Manager (PA-PM) on Operations at TCIP; the Port Legal Adviser (PLA); the Chief Port Tariff and Billing Officer (CTBO); the PRO for NCS for the TCIP Command; two staff each from Josepdam and Five Star Logistics (the private terminals).

3.3.3 Sources of Data

Primary sources used for the study includes questionnaires administered to port users and interviews conducted with port personnel.

Secondary sources used for the data were TCIP Annual Reports and NBS Reports on Port Statistics.

3.3.4 Research Instruments

Questionnaires administered to port users had twenty-three questions. The port users were drawn from truck drivers, clearing and forwarding agents, shipping company staff. The justification for choosing these categories of people as port users are based on the fact that they patronize TCIP on a day-to-day basis and have an idea of the services offered and the satisfaction derivative from the services rendered at the terminals. Responses from these respondents were presented in charts and tables with interpretations.

It should be noted that the questionnaire administered to port users was translated into three languages – English, Pidgin and Yoruba – to solidify the test of reliability in their responses.

Interviews were conducted with Port personnel which includes Nigeria Customs staff at TCIP, NPA TCIP staff, Private Terminal Operators' Staff). The justification for interviewing these port personnel is that they are the ones who make and mar port operations TCIP and are also part of the new port administration, following the use of the landlord model of port governance.

The audiotaped interviews were transcribed for coding along with themes and sub-themes. Patterns were drawn from transcribed interview using thematic content and narrative analysis.

3.3.5 Method of Data Presentation and Analysis

The data was sectioned into three parts. Data gotten from TCIP Annual Reports and NBS Report on Port Statistics was used to measure TCIP growth rate before and after concession. Port Performance at TCIP was statistically represented using Tables, Microsoft Excel Line Charts and Scatter Charts to show the trends in ship traffic, cargo throughput, turnaround time, vehicular traffic, berth occupancy and financial performance of the port complex.

Questionnaire response is the second section of the data collected for the study. All the 370 questionnaires administered were accounted for, even though not all the twenty-three questions contained in it were answered but the responses given were coded using Microsoft Excel before it was transferred to Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Interviews were also transcribed using thematic content analysis to separate emerging themes and sub-themes before they were used by the researcher in narrative format and triangulated with the questionnaire data. These data was used for further impact analysis of TCIP's concession.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Introduction

This chapter is a detailed presentation of the results of the study. The reports culled from the TCIP Annual Reports and NBS Port Statistics Data were aggregated and analyzed to validate Port Performance before and after concession using Tables, Line and Scattered Charts.

Data extracted from the respondents to the questionnaires administered were coded and analyzed using SPSS software to measure service delivery at TCIP using variables such as port user statistics, cargo clearance charges, warehouse facilities, transportation of cargoes, infrastructure issues and other challenges faced by port users at the TCIP. The interviews conducted were transcribed and triangulated with data gotten from the questionnaires administered.

The major findings from the research were discussed extensively while also validating research assumptions used for the study.

4.2 Measurement of Port Performance

According to United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD, 1976), port performance indicators to measure growth includes tonnage worked, berth occupancy rate, cargo handling, labour expenditure, capital equipment expenditure, arrival date, waiting time, service time, turnaround time, tonnage per ship, the fraction of time berthed ships worked, number of gangs employed. The data for the aforesaid indicators were extracted from the TCIP Annual Report (2003-2017) and the NBS Port Statistics (2012-2017), though, not all the indicators were captured in the annual reports but the researcher mined the ones captured to analyze pre-concession (2000-2006) and post-concession (2007-2017) growth rate at the TCIP.

4.2.1. Ship Traffic at the TCIP 2000 – 2017

The number of ships that entered the TCIP between 2002 and 2005 was 400-550, but it increased to 800 in 2006, when the port concession began and terminals were handed over to private terminals. The growth rate for ships that entered the TCIP was 70.3% in 2006 and that was the only time ship traffic increased by over 340. The growth rate of ship traffic after the concession was at 34.40% in 2007 but recorded a negative growth for three consecutive years.

Table 4.2.1a: Ship Traffic and Gross Registered Tonnage (GRT) at TCIP, 2000–2017

Year	Number of Ships Entered	GRT of Ships Entered	Ships Growth Rate (%)
2000	0	0	-
2001	0	0	-
2002	405	5,012,376	-
2003	549	6,147,587	35.56
2004	504	5,410,086	-8.20
2005	495	5,508,854	-1.79
2006	843	10,778,867	70.30
2007	1,133	15,803,871	34.40
2008	1,318	21,121,705	16.33
2009	1,359	24,005,688	3.11
2010	1,497	29,047,925	10.16
2011	1,628	32,702,604	8.75
2012	1,508	32,707,416	-7.37
2013	1,608	40,432,979	6.63
2014	1,698	46,851,102	5.60
2015	1,656	45,863,565	-2.47
2016	1,559	45,229,402	-5.86
2017	1,307	40,694,756	-16.16

Source: Tin Can Island Port Complex (TCIPC) Annual Report, 2003 & 2007 – 2017

The Gross Registered Tonnage (GRT) which is the tonnes weight for ships that entered the port before concession began was around 5,000,000 tonnes but it doubled in weight after the concession as seen in year 2007.

Figure 1: Ship Traffic and Gross Registered Tonnage (GRT) at the TCIP, 2000–2017

The increase in GRT for ships that entered TCIP recorded a huge spike in 2014 with 46,851,102 tonnes in correlation with number of ships that entered the port that same year.

Table 4.2.1b: Comparative Ship Traffic and GRT, 2012–2017

Year	Ports					
	Apapa	Tin Can Island	Rivers	Onne	Calabar	Delta
2007	1,359	1,133	455	733	897	272
2008	1,452	1,318	481	712	351	309
2009	1,545	1,389	459	686	321	321
2010	1,588	1,504	482	769	197	341
2011	1,594	1,628	548	885	179	362
2012	1,445	1,508	499	859	159	615
2013	1,510	1,615	439	823	373	609
2014	1,503	1,692	435	847	269	603
2015	1,410	1,656	373	741	306	528
2016	1,194	1,559	319	659	453	438
2017	1,154	1,307	309	671	403	448

National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) Nigerian Port Statistics, 2012 – 2017

A comparative analysis of ship traffic among the six port complexes revealed that the TCIP has the highest ship traffic in Nigerian ports since 2011, which means more ships come into TCIP than any other ports.

As there was increase in ships that entered the port, the turnaround time for these vessels after offloading their cargo was at 10.43 days in 2002, it only reduced by two days in 2006 which was during the pre-concession period, but in 2017, the average turnaround time for ships has reduced to four days. These positive impact can be attributed to the 24/7 operations that has been introduced at Tin Can, the sharing of duties between NPA and the private terminal operators which has changed operational procedures, workforce and equipment used at the port.

Table 4.2.1c: Average Turn-around Time for Ships

Year	Average Turn-around Time (Days)
2000	-
2001	-
2002	10.43
2003	8.18
2004	8.01
2005	9.01
2006	8.01
2007	7.01
2008	7.01
2009	6.6
2010	5.62
2011	4.27
2012	5.26
2013	4.35
2014	3.98
2015	4.13
2016	3.51
2017	3.99

Source: Tin Can Island Port Complex (TCIPC) Annual Report, 2003, 2007 – 2017

The growth rate of turnaround time during pre-concession was -23.20% but post-concession growth rate is at -43.08, this is a positive impact for the TCIP as ships can leave the ports within ninety-six hours after docking and offloading.

4.2.2 Cargo Throughput

In 2001, TCIP recorded a total cargo throughput of 6,816,685 tonnes with a growth rate of 73% but it dropped in 2003 to a negative growth rate. However, TCIP recorded a 34% growth rate in cargo throughput in 2005 with 6,310,575 tonnes, this was before port concession started in 2006. TCIP recorded an overall 87% growth rate before the concession began.

Table 4.2.2a: Total Cargo Throughput at TCIP before Concession, 2000 – 2006

Year	Inward Cargo	Outward Cargo	Total Cargo (tonnes)	Number of Ships Entered	Growth Rate (%)
2000	0	0	3,937,863	0	13.62
2001	0	0	6,816,685	0	73.11
2002	3,995,306	109,722	4,105,028	405	-39.78
2003	4,493,789	89,716	4,583,505	549	11.66
2004	0	0	4,693,860	504	2.41
2005	0	0	6,310,575	495	34.44
2006	7,208,318	163,644	7,371,962	843	16.82
Total Growth (Pre-Concession)					87.2

Source: Tin Can Island Port Complex (TCIPC) Annual Report, 2003 & 2007 - 2017

The table below showed that the highest growth rate recorded after port concession became operational was 39.76% in 2007 and it continued to spiral downward from that point, logging negative growth rate from 2015 to 2017.

Table 4.2.2b: Total Cargo Throughput at TCIP after Concession, 2007 – 2017

Year	Inward Cargo	Outward Cargo	Total Cargo (tonnes)	Number of Ships Entered	Growth Rate (%)
2007	10,046,217	257,043	10,303,260	1,133	39.76
2008	11,007,771	507,852	11,515,623	1,318	11.77
2009	12,946,927	594,089	13,541,016	1,359	17.59
2010	13,839,836	640,002	14,479,838	1,497	6.93

2011	15,583,779	646,812	16,230,591	1,628	12.09
2012	14,515,229	703,995	15,219,224	1,508	-6.23
2013	15,357,933	710,952	16,068,885	1,608	5.58
2014	16,483,099	1,020,208	17,503,307	1,698	8.93
2015	15,195,464	1,092,629	16,288,093	1,656	-6.94
2016	14,742,232	906,687	15,648,919	1,559	-3.92
2017	14,580,670	883,715	15,464,385	1,307	-1.18
Total Growth (Post-Concession)					50.1

Source: TCIPC Annual Report, 2007 – 2017

The scattered graph below showed that there was a progressive increase in ship traffic and cargo throughput at the TCIP until it started declining in 2015 leading to negative growth rate at the port.

Figure 2: Total Cargo Throughput and Ships Entered into TCIP, 2000-2017

TCIP is positioned as one of the most viable ports in Nigeria, however, data on cargo throughput within an 11-year period showed that the Lagos ports – Apapa and Tin Can – came second and third while Onne port had the highest cargo throughput. The reason for Onne’s lead

in cargo throughput during the post-concession period is based on the fact that the port has been practicing Landlord model before port concession was officially operationalized, this was captured by Pinwa (1999) with his dissertation that focused on measuring port performance at the Eastern port.

Table 4.2.2c: Comparative Cargo Throughput at TCIP after Concession, 2012 – 2017

Year	Ports					
	Apapa	Tin Can Island	Rivers	Onne	Calabar	Delta
2007	18,567,253	10,003,300	4,878,757	21,558,925	949,523	1,515,592
2008	20,709,226	12,807,920	4,894,111	22,011,200	1,245,599	2,214,693
2009	18,914,562	13,541,016	5,141,451	17,215,120	1,721,249	6,590,471
2010	21,239,855	14,461,638	5,808,533	23,832,763	1,594,277	9,807,661
2011	22,808,353	16,230,591	7,463,620	26,529,884	1,878,753	8,538,831
2012	19,951,807	15,268,897	5,574,653	27,580,642	1,723,195	6,987,533
2013	20,437,369	16,134,153	4,935,944	24,773,387	1,732,286	10,361,746
2014	20,645,269	17,500,804	6,225,008	27,968,861	2,361,477	10,199,169
2015	20,250,771	16,407,133	4,457,785	26,314,828	2,127,259	7,829,862
2016	19,055,385	15,648,919	3,574,235	23,434,241	2,329,984	6,836,616
2017	19,099,690	15,464,385	3,536,873	26,049,226	2,187,689	5,197,773

Source: NPA (2018)

The above comparative throughput showed that TCIP had significant improvement in cargo throughput having maintained the third spot out of six ports for eleven years. Though, the growth rate for TCIP pre and post-concession revealed that the port had more positive growth before the concession than it did after.

4.2.3 Berth Occupancy

Table 4.2.3: Berth Occupancy Rate

Year	Berth Occupancy Rate (%)
2000	57
2001	N/A
2002	68

2003	72
2004	47
2005	55
2006	73
2007	87
2008	54
2009	72
2010	73
2011	65
2012	70
2013	68
2014	65
2015	54
2016	55
2017	56

Source: Tin Can Island Port Complex (TCIPC) Annual Report, 2003, 2007 – 2017

There is a correlation between berth occupancy and port productivity. UNCTAD (1976) analysis posits that high berth occupancy is a sign of congestion (>70%) showing a decline of services, while low berth occupancy signifies underutilization of resources (<50%). Before port concession, the data shows that the TCIP was on the verge of underutilization before it moved to a congested port at 73%.

Figure 3: Berth Occupancy Rate at the TCIP 2000 – 2017

After the concession, it struggled to break even which happened in 2008. Since 2012, TCIP has stayed within the 50 – 70% range with a steady drop from 70% but the data for 2017 shows that it is tethering within underutilization again. The investment in port infrastructure and sharing of operations as cited by the researcher during fieldwork at the port area has been instrumental in improving port utilization.

4.2.4 Financial Performance

TCIP's generated revenue was over a billion naira before the government conceived the idea of port reforms, but it started having operational deficit when its expenditure surpassed generated revenue in 2004, which could be attributed to the labour issues and workforce downsizing when the process for port concession began.

After TCIP experienced the last operational deficit in 2007, it has maintain a favourable balance of payment, netting double of what it made in surplus in pre-concession period.

Table 4.2.4: Revenue Generated and Operating Expenditure at TCIP, 2000-2017

Year	Generated Revenue		Operating Expenditure	Operating Surplus/Deficit
	Naira (₦)	Dollar (\$)	Naira (₦)	Naira (₦)
2000	0	0	0	0
2001	0	0	0	0
2002	1,070,000,000.00	39,600,000.00	2,340,000.00	1,067,660,000.00
2003	1,610,000,000.00	44,730,000.00	2,300,000.00	1,607,700,000.00
2004	1,500,000,000.00	54,550,000.00	2,000,000,000.00	-500,000,000.00
2005	2,160,000,000.00	39,630,000.00	2,510,000,000.00	-350,000,000.00
2006	2,074,050,126.96	10,404,347,658.00	682,033,390.05	1,392,016,736.91
2007	688,219,408.70	53,648,410.16	1,446,967,025.63	-758,747,616.93
2008	870,139,980.09	119,603,258.36	447,995,660.88	422,144,319.21
2009	2,362,863,809.79	125,270,690.24	600,178,897.34	1,762,684,912.45
2010	2,274,234,063.17	144,017,005.70	659,859,368.50	1,614,374,694.67
2011	1,784,507,561.19	136,386,324.70	748,800,000.00	1,035,707,561.19
2012	2,350,000,000.00	117,310,000.00	928,600,000.00	1,421,400,000.00
2013	1,833,295,160.00	167,238,083.70	974,261,068.00	859,034,092.00
2014	3,065,095,616.83	174,097,522.80	780,598,658.61	2,284,496,958.22
2015	1,877,209,453.93	141,321,729.69	619,409,565.00	1,257,799,888.93

2016	1,774,072,969.95	154,242,074.60	665,587,017.42	1,108,485,952.53
2017	3,375,371,801.91	151,655,295.08	872,754,335.88	2,502,617,466.03

Source: Tin Can Island Port Complex (TCIPC) Annual Report, 2003, 2007 – 2017

In 2014 and 2017, the TCIP recorded over two billion naira in operational surplus which significant growth for the post-concession period. As observed, this surplus which is not limited to TCIP only has increased the NPA’s contribution to the country’s coffers.

4.3 Measurement of Service Delivery at the TCIP

To deepen the measurement of TCIP’s performance, the study examined certain indices of service delivery. The questionnaires administered to port users (truck drivers, clearing and forwarding agents, and shipping company staff) and interviews conducted with Port personnel (Nigeria Customs staff at TCIP, NPA TCIP staff, Private Terminal Operators’ Staff) were coined to give insights into patronage at the port, ships and vessels operations, materials used, resources and labour expended by port stakeholders, infrastructure at port areas and activities of port authorities.

All the questionnaires were administered to the respondents, who were given the label ‘port users,’ which include Clearing and Forwarding Agents, Shipping Company Staff and Truck drivers. The 370 questionnaires were all accounted for, however, not all the twenty-three (23) questions contained in the questionnaires were answered in full, but the data generated from the responses to the questionnaire have been classified into three sections – the socio-economic data of respondents, the efficiency of service delivery at TCIP before port concession, service delivery at the TCIP after port concession and Improvement on Service Delivery issues at the TCIP.

Also, the data gotten from the transcribed interviews were triangulated with the data mined from the questionnaire responses.

4.3.1 Socio-Economic Data of Respondents

The socio-economic data of the respondents that were collected include gender, age, marital status, educational qualification but only that of employment station is relevant to this study.

Table 4.3.1.1: Distribution of respondents by Employment

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Clearing Agent	192	51.9
Shipping Company Staff	7	1.9
Driver	171	46.2
Others	0	0
Total	370	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2019

From the table above, the distribution of the respondents by employment station shows that the highest respondents to the questions are Clearing Agents (51.9%) and Truck Drivers (46.2%).

4.3.2. Port Users Patronage at the TCIP

This was measured using the responses gotten from port users' about their patronage of the TCIP before and after the concession. The data was triangulated with insights drawn from interviews conducted with port personnel on the challenges of service delivery faced at the port before its concession.

Table 4.3.2.1: Number of Years as TCIP User

Variables	Numbers of Years As Tin Can Island Port User				Total
	Less than 1 year	1 – 5 years	6 – 10 years	11 years – above	
Clearing Agent	0	95	66	31	192
Shipping Company Staff	0	7	0	0	7

Driver	22	89	60	0	171
Total	22	191	126	31	370

Source: Fieldwork, 2019

The data from the table shows that out of the 370 respondents, 8.4% of the respondents (11 years and above) have been using the port before its concession while the remaining 91.4% represent users that started using the port ten years ago, depicting that there is a positive relationship between port concession and increase in the number of users at the TCIP.

To put it in perspective, during interview sessions with port personnel who have been the staff of the government agencies and private terminals, they shared tidbits about the state of the port before its concession and why concession has been beneficial.

According to the Port Legal Adviser (PLA) of the Tin Can Island Port:

Before they (private operators) came in, the turnaround time for vessels could take two months to clear two vessels and...then, we had a lot of equipment lying fallow, damaged, stolen, accountability was not easy because the workforce was so many but with the concession, they downsized the workforce at the port which was terrible (Personal communication, July 11, 2019).

Also, the Customs PRO for the TCIP command stated that:

When government mooted the idea of concession, they surveyed the port where they saw that the ports weren't efficiently managed in the sense that there were all manners of challenges and irregularities in port operations and system (Personal communication, October 7, 2019).

Shedding more light on the state of Nigerian port when it was handed over to private investors, a staff at the private terminal stated that:

The handing over was a nightmare, they had overtime, cargoes that couldn't be accounted for because they didn't have proper records for it (Personal communication, October 10, 2019).

All these points to some of the inefficiency inherent in port operations before it was handed over to private terminals through the concession process.

4.3.3 Port Users’ and Personnel Perspectives on Service Delivery at the TCIP after Concession

This was analyzed and discussed using three port impact assessment indicators - Impact of Port Concession on Port Terminals Patronage; Impact of Concession on Port Resources, Impact of Concession on Port Infrastructure, and Port Authorities and Service Delivery Issues at the TCIP.

4.3.3.1 Impact of Port Concession on Port Terminals Patronage

Table 4.3.3.1a: TCIP Terminals Frequented by port users

Variables	Terminals Used Frequently at TCIP					Total
	FSL	JPS	SIFAX Group	PTML	TICT	
Clearing Agent	74	7	23	67	21	192
Shipping Company Staff	0	0	0	7	0	7
Driver	44	29	7	0	91	171
Total	118	36	30	74	112	370

Source: Fieldwork, 2019

The data from respondents show that the TCIP is being patronized based on the cargo type being handled at the various terminals. More port users frequented FSL due to fact that it had one of the best RORO terminals at the Lagos ports, while TICT had more users as it is a full-time container terminal which is easy to navigate. Poor security is a major challenge at the port, especially in pre-concession period which led to theft and stealing of cargo, hence, one of the questions on the questionnaire inquired about usage of warehouse facilities which have been largely invested in by the private terminals.

Table 4.3.3.1b: Usage of warehouse facilities at the TCIP

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Terminal Operators' Warehouse	179	48.4
NPA Tin Can Island Warehouse	60	16.2
Clearing Agents' Warehouse	8	2.2
Others	35	9.5
Total	282	76.2

Source: Fieldwork, 2019

76.2% of the 370 respondents that answered this question revealed that they felt safe using the port warehouse, unlike what was obtained before the port concession. These responses showed that the terminal operators' warehouse which 48.4% of the respondents used was safer and more economical, due to its proximity. As observed by the researcher, the improvement in warehouse facilities is quite obvious, as these terminal operators now offer storage charges to containers and vehicles at their terminal which is a win-win situation for the agents.

Not only that, one of the interviewees revealed that some RoRo terminals grant waivers on storage charges to their customers, which makes it more preferable for port users. There is a reduced charge for terminal operators' warehouse and containers get free warehousing days before the charges for paid warehousing starts counting. Also, some of the agents use the NPA warehouse which is popularly known as bonded terminals or off-dock terminals because some of them are much closer to the port exit areas.

Table 4.3.3.1c: Cargo Transportation after Concession

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Yes	356	96.2
No	7	1.9
Indifferent	0	0
Total	363	98.1

Source: Fieldwork, 2019

Out of 98.1% of the 370 respondents answered the question, 96.2% asserted that there is an improvement to transportation of cargo after concession. A truck driver sampled by the researcher revealed that some private terminals have a warehouse close to the port exit route where truck drivers can go to claim their containers. Also some terminals are located close to the port exit route, which makes it easier to transport cargoes out of the port.

The perspective of port users and personnel unanimously stated that there port concession affected cargo transport of cargo after clearance at the port. According to multiple interviewees, it took weeks, even months to leave the port in pre-concession period due to congestion on the roads, but it has been streamlined to make it comfortable for outgoing cargoes and containers.

Table 4.3.3.1d: Time Duration for Transporting Cleared Cargoes

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Days	348	94.1
Weeks	15	4.1
Months	0	0
Total	363	98.1

Source: Fieldwork, 2019

In furtherance of the researcher’s inquiry into post-concession performance at the port, respondents were asked how long it takes them to transport their goods from the ports after clearance. 94.1% of the 370 respondents answered that it took them days to transport their cargoes out of the port, while 4.1% said it took them weeks.

During interview sessions with port personnel, service delivery was put forward as a question to get opinions on services delivery before and after concession, one of the personnel interviewed stated that:

It was a good thing the port was put up for concession and workforce downsized and like it is when you are starting a new business, there are always things you don’t get right but with time, when you continue, you streamline and stabilize and put things in order and we’re seeing the result with improved service delivery at the port terminals (Personal communication, July 11, 2019).

In corroboration to the aforesaid, another port terminal staff stated that:

If you look at the merit of the concession, you will see that some mechanized equipment that hitherto wasn't there, like the obsolete crane system has been eased off, paving way for rubber-tired cranes which are available at some of these terminals that can move larger numbers of containers within split seconds, that has helped in ensuring faster service delivery at the port, contrary to what we had before.....concession has ensured that larger turnaround of cargo, the quantity being handled now is different from what they were handling before, these and many other port operations have been improved on by the private operators, unlike what we have before (Personal communication, October 7, 2019).

As shared by an official at NPA Tin Can Island, he opined that:

Service delivery has improved when we look at most of the terminals or the terminal operators that bring in heavy machines like the RTG which is a fast-moving crane machine when we also look at the turnaround time of a vessel, it has improved (Personal Communication, June 25, 2019).

Another top official at the TCIP corroborated the aforesaid assertion saying:

Service delivery has improved because these private investors brought in modern equipment that has helped to improve port operations and there has been some kind of sanity at the port since they took over the terminals (Personal Communication, September 25, 2019).

The data collated from the questionnaire and deductions from the interviews revealed that port users at the TCIP has improved due to service delivery performance in warehousing facilities and duration of cargo transportation when compared to what was obtained before concession.

4.3.3.2 Impact of Concession on Port Resources

Port resources includes clearance procedure, handling rate of discharge operation, waiting time, operating cost, degree of flexibility in resource usage and overall time at the port. The questionnaire asked users about their perspectives on port resources at the TCIP.

Table 4.3.3.2a: Improvement in cargo clearance procedure

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Yes	320	86.5
No	14	3.8

Indifferent	0	0
Total	334	90.3

Source: Fieldwork, 2019

Most of the respondents had a positive response to this question, even though not all the 370 respondents answered this question, but 95.8% of those that answered stated that the clearance procedure has improved at the TCIP. This implies that there is a positive impact of concession on cargo clearance procedure. Several literature on pre-concession revealed that port operations were conducted traditionally, but from data gathered and observations, the process has been streamlined now using technology. During my interview with several administrators at the port, an interviewee at the private terminal gave a brief tutorial on using the NPA TCIP online portal to generate manifest for incoming cargoes or shipments, explaining that terminal operators get their manifest mailed to them within twenty-four hours. The customs clearance procedure has been moved to an e-portal too, where clearance agents have login IDs to generate charges for the cargo they want to clear before they present it to the customs office for filing and official authorization.

It would be recalled that following port concession, a pact was made to digitize its operations, which took effect in February 2017. The guidelines to transfer operations to electronic portals were launched as part of the 60-Day National Action Plan on Ease of Doing Business by the Presidential Enabling Business Environment Council (PEBEC) but it has become a policy action which the agencies involved in port operation abide by stringently. This was confirmed by a port terminal official when questioned on cargo clearance procedure –

At the NPA, they have made their process seamless now, the billing system is automated. I just converted a vessel that has over one thousand containers with detailed information on each cargo on that vessel, ordinarily it would have required someone to go through all this information at the NPA but with the automation, it takes just hours for the bill to be ready. As it is, the vessel will be reaching here tomorrow and the bill will be ready before it does, which I am certain of, which is something we can't boast of before when we had to monitor it manually (Personal communication, October 10, 2019).

Also, the Customs Official confirmed that:

The issue of electronic manifest, before any cargo leaves any part of the world, the shippers must send advance manifest to the customs, which is in line with international standard. This manifest spells out to the Customs everything contained on the port vessel, all the containers with their details. Once the cargo arrives, what we normally do is the profiling and cargo selectivity, using our technical expertise to isolate and check some of these cargoes to know which ones have high risk, which ones are low risk. Also, we do a matching of what's contained in the electronic manifest sent to us and the hard copy brought in by the agent to see if there's a correlation, once it's ascertained you've met all the requirements, you have no issues at all with clearance. We (customs) check for complete documentation, no infraction with the trade extant policies including but not limited to non-dutiable goods and smuggled or prohibited goods (Personal communication, October 7, 2019).

When the official was questioned on the issue of cargo examination, he explained that:

The Customs being given the role of lead agency at the port, we cannot afford to be seen wavering from our role, in essence, we've ensured that Customs notifies everyone when there is to be an inspection of cargo, so that all agencies can get their representatives to be at a designated place for joint examination of cargoes, so the issue of after customs have examined a cargo, SON coming to say it's not satisfied has been confined to the abyss of history. When you get to the terminals, you'll see designated places marked for joint examination of all agencies, in these places, we start the examination by 10am and before that day, the agencies would have gotten Bill of Lading that they'll use for the examination of the cargo, also the terminal operators would have dropped the container to be examined at the inspection area before the inspection day, once the agencies arrive at the terminal, we all perform our duties, depart the terminal and write our joint reports. For now, that's the process for cargo examination, nothing like one agency goes to the terminal for an independent examination of cargoes (Personal communication, October 7, 2019).

Before the revised guideline, Nigeria required up to fourteen (14) documents for imports compared to just five (5) in Rwanda (BPSR, 2017) but the directive the streamline guidelines has made agencies like the Customs make its cargo clearance operations automated, it was confirmed by the Customs official, thus:

Customs is automated, what we use for the e-clearance process is called Nigeria Integrated Customs Information System 2 (NICIS 2) towards ensuring trade facilitation. We started with NICIS 1 but we've upgraded to NICIS 2 which is an improvement from the first one which had loopholes but the current ones have been corrected (Personal communication, October 7, 2019).

The Customs accredit clearing agents or freight forwarders as each of them have unique log-in information that they use for transactions on the NICIS 2 portal for cargo clearance of any kind, the top Customs officer states that:

If you're not licensed, the system wouldn't recognize you. Once you login your entry to the e-portal and your license isn't valid, you're logged out of the system. If there are transactions that a licensed agent has done that have put your license to question, we block the license and invite you to come and explain what happened to us (Personal communication, October 7, 2019).

Also, terminal operators have an e-portal where agents can also generate waybills and invoices that will be presented at terminal gates before picking up their consignment. Nonetheless, the researcher still asked the port users how long it takes them to clear their cargoes.

Table 4.3.3.2b: Time spent for Cargo Clearance by port users

Variables	Time Duration of Cargo Clearance at Tin Can Island Port			Total
	Days	Weeks	Months	
Clearing Agent	149	43	0	192
Shipping Company Staff	0	0	7	7
Driver	0	163	8	171
Total	149	206	15	370

Source: Fieldwork, 2019

The World Development Indicators (WDI, 2019) report on the average time to clear exports through customs (days) shows that Albania, Azerbaijan, Estonia, Croatia, Greece, Ireland, Romania, Serbia and Thailand has a maximum number of four days to achieve customs clearance but most African countries have an average between 6 to 20 days including Nigeria, which shows in the data gotten from the fieldwork at the TCIP.

During fieldwork, clearing agents shared with the researcher that it takes days, rolling into weeks to clear imported cargoes, containers or cars, while for drivers, it takes them weeks to beat the queue leading to the terminals, present documentation to pick certain containers at the

gate, loading it and transporting it out of the port. In light of this, here are some responses as regards agencies where port users face challenges during cargo clearance.

Table 4.3.3.2c: Agencies where Port Users face challenges during cargo clearance

Variables	Frequency	Percent
NPA (TCIP) Admin	0	0
Shipping Company	0	0
Nigeria Customs Service	148	40.0
Terminal Operators	52	14.1
All of the above	7	1.9
Total	207	55.9

Source: Fieldwork, 2019

55.9% of the 370 respondents who responded to the question on the challenges faced at the port stated that they had issues with cargo clearance, 40% of the respondents had pending issues with the Customs, 14.1% of the respondents had issues with terminal operators while 1.9% had challenges with all the agencies involved in the process of cargo clearance.

According to these respondents, challenges they had with these agencies ranged from authorization of clearance charges, duplication of duties, pending waybills, damage of cargoes during offloading at the dock, for some, late pickup of cargoes from points of destination.

The data showed that there is a unique relationship between port concession and challenges faced during cargo clearance, for instance, the challenges faced at the port before concession had to do with overstaffing, underutilization of the port, congestion and low service delivery but since concession, the challenges has shifted to more administrative and technical issues.

During the interview session, the Customs' PRO was asked why his agency caused an excess delay during cargo clearance and inspection, he explained that:

Before now, Customs was doing the job of NAFDAC, NDLEA, etc. but since the establishment of these agencies, their duties have been removed from what the Customs does, so they do it independently now. For us at the Customs, our job remains the collection of revenue and accounting for it as well as putting a stop to smuggling.

NAFDAC is a regulatory agency, if you want to bring in food and drinks, you must have NAFDAC certification before you bring it into the country, same for NDLEA, NESREA or SON, they are the regulatory agencies. However, we work in sync as no agency can work in isolation at the port, we're complementing each other, whenever we see anything related to the functions of NDLEA, NESREA, NAFDAC or Plant Quarantine we call their attention to it (Personal Communication, October 7, 2019).

Following the clarification given by the Customs official, some staff of the terminal operators believe that even without the duplication of duties during cargo clearance, the Customs causes more delays in terms of processing cargo clearance charges, which also affects their operations, it was clarified thus:

The only issue we have is the clearing agents' payment of duties to Customs, which does not affect us directly, it takes days for the agents to pay their customs duties and get official authorization from customs on releasing their cargo or goods, which is more on the Customs side (Personal Communication, October 10, 2019).

To put it into perspective, the questionnaire quizzed port users on charges and operation cost for clearing their cargo at the port, below is the data mined from their responses.

Table 4.3.3.2d: Range of amount charged for cargo clearance

Variables	Frequency	Percent
N101,000 – N200,000	8	2.2
N201,000 – N500,000	90	24.3
N501,000 – above	94	25.4
Total	192	51.9

Source: Fieldwork, 2019

49.7% of the 370 respondents that answered the question stated that they paid over two hundred thousand naira and above for cargo clearance at the port. The researcher noted that there has been a shift in operation cost after the concession as private terminals were given the financial autonomy on price fixing for cargo clearance. Over the years, the naira to dollar exchange rate (which is the ultimate determinant for port charges) has also made operating cost for cargo

clearance increase. The total charges for cargo clearance and importation is estimated at millions of naira depending on the TEU and tonnes for the container.

Based on the aforesaid, port users shared insight on agencies and operation cost.

Table 4.3.3.2e: Agencies with High Operation Cost during Cargo Clearance

Variables	Frequency	Percent
NPA (TCIP) Admin	0	0
Shipping Company	21	5.7
Nigeria Customs Service	178	48.1
Terminal Operators	0	0
Total	199	53.8

Source: Fieldwork, 2019

53.8% of the 370 respondents that answered this question stated that they paid more for cargo clearance with the Shipping companies and Nigeria Customs Service.

It should be noted that when it comes to cargo clearance after the vessel arrives at the port, the NPA has minimal operational jurisdiction after it has transmitted e-Manifest to the terminal operators and shipping company. The charges on cargo clearance is solely within the purview of the Customs, so when the interviewer inquired about the charges, the Customs PRO clarified that on charges –

The content of the cargo determines the Customs clearance charge, you'll find more information on it in the Common External Tariff (CET).....all the items on the surface of the earth have a tariff heading and classification. For instance, anything about vehicles is in chapter 87; Livestock like cattle, you'll find information for it in Chapter 1; Papers and other stationery is in Chapter 48. The CET we're using now covers 2012 to 2019 (Personal communication, October 7, 2019).

After this was clarified, the researcher inquired about the fluctuating exchange rate of dollars which is the major currency used in cargo charges and the Customs official hinted that:

That's a federal government policy, within the purview of the Federal Ministry of Finance, once they transmit the current exchange rate to us, we start to implement it. Customs have nothing to do with the exchange rate, we're only there to make sure the

functions of government which are implementation and enforcement of fiscal policies are being carried out (Personal communication, October 7, 2019).

In light of this, the terminal operator also complained about the fluctuating exchange rate and its unavailability to the clearing agents which hurts their operations, however, when they were asked about how they determine the charges for cargo clearance at their port, an official explained that it depends on the metric tonnes for the cargo being cleared, in the case of vehicular clearance, it was stated that there are four types – cars, vans, trucks and plants which has its varied prices. Another terminal operator staff clarified further that:

The price range comes in different forms but for vehicles, the dues charged on it depends on the vehicle's year of production. However, our terminal charges is constant and depending on the storage period, once it stays longer, storage due is high (Personal communication, October 10, 2019).

Meanwhile, when the interviewer put forth the question on how NPA regulates cargo clearance charges, a TCIP official stated that:

When we talk of cargo and when we talk of charges, they are very complex term but when you say charges on a cargo, each terminal operator has been able to come up with the charges they can bear, the NPA cannot force them to reduce their charges as they are all in competition. If a terminal is fast in cargo delivery, using super-structural machines, its charges will be different from that of the one that uses manual and always late in clearance and delivery, to me, the terminal operators are at liberty to handle their operations but under the eagle eye of the NPA, but when the stakeholder or the customers raise an alarm, the NPA will look into it (Personal Communication, June 25, 2019).

4.3.3.3 Impact of Concession on Port Infrastructure

Infrastructure is a central part of service delivery, to measure port performance it would not be amiss analyse the impact of infrastructure which has been a major challenge in Nigerian ports before concession. Port users were asked about the inherent challenges of the TCIP and below is their responses.

Table 4.3.3.3a: Causes of Challenges faced during Cargo Clearance

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Corruption	16	4.3
Delay by Staff	29	7.8
Lack of manpower	0	0
Lack of infrastructure facilities	177	47.8
All of the above	0	0
Total	222	60.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2019

60% of the 370 respondents that answered the question on particular challenges they faced at these terminals or during cargo clearance responded that the major challenge to cargo clearance was the lack of infrastructure facilities at the port. The respondents stated that the infrastructure which the port lacks is the access roads and machinery used for checking cargoes which made port operations slow.

During an interview with NPA and Customs officials, equipment issue was brought up and the NPA official confirmed that the quay apron at some terminals had collapsed at some terminals but the NPA was doing something about it. When that line of questioning was followed up with the issue of scanners, NPA officials said it was the function of Customs to provide scanners used for examination at the terminals.

An online search for news articles on scanners confirmed that the federal government approved the purchase of scanners in February 2019, when the Customs PRO was questioned on the availability of the scanners, he was quoted saying:

Like you said now, the government has approved the purchase of scanners but they're not over-the-counter purchases because they come in many shapes and variations as well as specifications that meets your peculiarity, so it takes time before they're manufactured and eventually delivered to us. We've been having challenges on the scanner because the ones we inherited are obsolete and un-serviceable, before the federal government approved the purchase of new ones, even before then, the Comptroller General of Customs, Col. Hammed Ali, has mentioned it at various fora on the federal government's intention to purchase scanners, we're glad they're following it up. For now, we're doing 100 percent manual examination of cargoes till

the new scanners arrive to improve our operations for better productivity (Personal Communication, October 7, 2019).

His response also confirms that the manual inspection of cargo causes delay in cargo inspection and clearance, considering the weight of a container that needs to be examined and the content of the container which will be quite enormous.

Meanwhile, 4.3% of the respondents to table 4.3.3.4a stated that corruption is still one of the challenges at the port, stating that there are still many forward and backward linkages in port operations especially during clearance of cargo at Customs and Private Terminals. Also, 7.8% of the respondents, said the major challenges at the port was caused by delay by staff at some of the agencies but declined to state which agency's staff causes delay to cargo clearance.

However, the researcher identified some key issues that continue to plague port operations at TCIP are lack of manpower, inaccessible roads, corruption, and excess delay. When these indices were presented as a factor to low service delivery at the port, this is what the officials of NPA and Customs said:

I will not say lack of manpower, because when we say manpower, we look at it in broader terms, to me, the problem is not manpower, it is inaccessible or bad roads because when we look at the road network, it has been abandoned for a long period. Again, there is no expansion to support the demands which we all know that we are a consumer country, where we consume a lot, because of that our infrastructure should be able to handle the quantity of cargo coming out of the port. To me, I think the infrastructure greatly affects service delivery (Personal Communication, June 25, 2019).

When we say corruption or excess delay, I do not know how to quantify that, but to me, I will say what are the causes of delay should be a factor we have to look into. What causes the delay? Is it the government agencies, through duplication of duties? Because to me, I can't see why the Customs will examine cargo and you are saying another body should do the same type of work, these are the things the government has to look into. There are some agencies, government agencies that need to leave the port, strictly, they should be called upon on a specialized product that concerns them. To me, they shouldn't open all examinations of cargo to all government agencies. In my own opinion, the excess delay is more embedded in poor service delivery through duplication of duties, not corruption (Personal Communication, June 25, 2019).

Both of them (manpower and inaccessible roads) causes low and ineffective service delivery but at varying degrees like manpower, that one causes affect service delivery but that of the inaccessible road is much higher when we look at it because every port users and staff is feeling its effect which also has an impact on service delivery (Personal Communication, July 11, 2019).

The same question was put forth to the staff of terminal operators which was clarified, thus:

We have sufficient manpower in our terminal but our basic challenge is the access roads which is the function of the NPA and the federal government (Personal Communication, October 7, 2019).

Manpower, no! But access road is a national problem and a man-made problem because those in charge of it have not taken the needed measures to end it (Personal Communication, October 10, 2019).

From access to the port, they're already collecting money, for trucks to get in to load, they spend more than 20,000 naira, is that not corruption?! It is not only that, even on the side of customs, they're not innocent, then the agents too put bottlenecks which is to extort and causes an unnecessary delay for cargo clearance. Also, the NPA is culpable here too, as they are taking undue advantage to control access into the port which they don't have control over, rather than leave it to the port police to handle (Personal Communication, October 10, 2019).

All the aforesaid insights given by port personnel confirms that lack of infrastructure was a recurring issue at the port. Research and observation also revealed that 'inaccessible roads' is one of the major issues that continue to trail Nigerian ports, especially the Apapa and Tin Can Island ports, even after concession.

The waiting queue of trailers and trucks waiting to get to the port entrance and terminals to take delivery of cargoes is an unending one which has led to congestion of Lagos roads like the Eko Bridge, Surulere, Mile 2 area, Apapa-Oshodi expressway and other side roads within Apapa, Coconut and Mile 2 area. However, port users were cross-questioned on how inaccessible road affects them.

Table 4.3.3.3b: Inaccessible road causes delay in cargo clearance

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Yes	362	97.8
No	0	0
Maybe	0	0
Total	362	97.8

Source: Fieldwork, 2019

97.8% of the 370 respondents to this question were unequivocal that inaccessible roads causes delay to cargo clearance at the TCIP. Further questioning on the effects of inaccessible roads, led to inquiry about time duration spent by drivers who want to gain access into the port.

Table 4.3.3.3c: Duration of Time Spent by Drivers on TCIP Road Queue

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Days	37	10.0
Weeks	178	48.1
Month	0	0
Total	215	58.1

Source: Fieldwork, 2019

58.1% of the 370 respondents, especially truck drivers when asked how long they had been on the queue stated that they had been on the queue for days counting into two weeks and more to get into the TCIP area, some of the respondents that had made it into the TCIP area, close to the first gate have been moving on the same queue between two days to three to get to the gate and make it to the terminals where they had containers to pick up.

From observation, inaccessible roads to the port is a major challenge, whenever it rains around the axis to the port, it slows down port operations as the roads become inaccessible for port users or they have to pay exorbitant prices for motorcycles which is the only transport means to get quick access into port area.

An official of the NPA at the TCIP affirmed the agency's failure to solve the issue of accessible roads, stating that:

It is road because they are blaming NPA, everybody is blaming NPA for the inaccessible roads to the port even though the issue of the road construction has political intonations which everybody should know. Albeit, they know that it has political undertones but they still go ahead to blame the NPA. There is a lot of politics in play when it comes to the construction of roads leading to the port but what can the NPA do (Personal Communication, July 11, 2019).

Almost all terminal operators when asked what affects service delivery, they went for inaccessible roads, when they were also asked to suggest what they want the federal government to do that will improve service delivery at their terminals, they said the accessible road was the only thing they wanted as it will tell on their output.

The researcher observed that the current transportation situation at the TCIP using the Apapa-Oshodi expressway route continues to worsen, buses can no longer navigate the route, only bike riders can use the dilapidated road which comes with an expensive price tag. Using the Apapa Wharf road to enter the TCIP doesn't fare better too, even though buses can ply the road. Trailers are parked haphazardly on the flyover bridges, main roads have been closed off due to the congestion or street parking by the trailer driver, some trailers have been abandoned by the roads, causing more gridlock to the bad road. Incidents of unsecured containers falling off the trailer while navigating the bad roads have become regular news in Nigeria's media.

Further observation revealed that inaccessible roads around port areas have extended to residential roads with trailers parked inside these streets, causing roadblocks, accidents, amongst other ills. Recently, another presidential directive was given to decongest the port and clear the roads, the fourth directive since the Buhari's administration took office, even with the task force set up to back this new directive, it has recorded little to no success at the TCIP.

In light of this challenge, the questionnaire contained a question seeking port users' opinion on using alternate means of transport like railway for goods and passengers.

Table 4.3.3.3d: Alternate to railway for transport of cleared cargoes

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Yes	279	75.4
No	51	13.8
Indifferent	40	10.8
Total	370	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2019

75% of all the respondents who were given the questionnaire agreed that there was a need for alternative transport for cargoes besides the road and they stated that would consider using the railway transport to move cargo out of the port areas after the railway becomes operational.

4.3.3.4 Port Authorities and Service Delivery Issues

Data and Deductions from interviews revealed that service delivery in port operations has moved from the inefficiency and ineptitude obtainable while it was solely managed and regulated by the NPA but there are still inherent service delivery issues. When the researcher posed questions to NPA-TCIP and Customs staff on how they will continue to boost service delivery, this is what they said:

The FG through the NPA is also exploring so many ways to improve service delivery at the port but I think the encouragement by the authority to terminals to use ‘Soft Badges’ for their operations has achieved remarkable success, thereby improving service delivery (Personal Communication, June 25, 2019).

Exploring the use of barges and dry ports, with that of Niger and Kaduna also in operation now (Personal Communication, July 11, 2019).

For now, the railway transport link is still the most active policy that I think needs to be explored, they will link up the railway line from Apapa to Tin Can Island, they just started the construction of the railway line at Apapa port, after that, it will be linked to Tin Can Island Port (Personal Communication, September 25, 2019).

We’ve developed a lot of templates. Like the Dispute Resolution Committee which was created by the command to make sure that in the process of this clearing business, any matter that arises between the agent and customs are channeled to this committee. We’ve got the help desk too, the PR unit serves as a help desk too, if you’ve got questions, you come here to inquire and the ones we can’t clarify, we refer you to the appropriate departments. These are deliberate creations of the CAC to ease services

rendered to customers, importers and clearing agents (Personal Communication, October 10, 2019).

When the same question was posed to terminal operators, the staff interviewed explained that:

Investment in equipment goes a long way in cargo discharge and we have seen a positive outcome on how it has made our operations much faster and efficient (Personal Communication, October 7, 2019).

Improving in our systems because we render services that are computer and tech-based now, so every day we try to imbibe new methods of service delivery, moving from the crude. For instance, we are trying to acquire handheld systems, you know you can't carry your laptops into the terminal, last month, we acquired some handheld systems that can be used to capture data by those at the ship side, the system can even scan and have keypads that you can use to fill in quick information on vessels or the owner and go straight to our e-portal. We want a situation where we can limit human interference in the exchange for data and information in cargo clearance (Personal Communication, October 10, 2019).

We have deployed ICT to manage our operations, we called it Terminal Operating System (TOS). We have acquired machines for uninterrupted delivery of cargoes. We have deployed the Terminal Management System of international practice to make service delivery seamless (Personal Communication, October 10, 2019).

All of the measures mentioned by the port stakeholders are good decisions to improve productivity and service delivery.

4.4 Discussion of Research Findings

Measuring port performance requires analyzing various indicators within the port systems, for this study, the researcher choose to use the classification of performance indicators developed by Mahfouz and Arisha (2009) which categorized indicators under the headings of Ships/Vessels, Resources, Materials Infrastructure and Port Authorities.

Table 4.4: Port Growth Rate at TCIP from 2000 to 2017

Year	Ship Traffic (Entered)		ATAT (Days)	Cargo Throughput (Tonnes)				Berth Occupancy Rate (%)	Generated Revenue (₹)	Operating Surplus/Deficit (₹)
	No.	Growth rate (%)		Inward	Outward	Total	Growth Rate (%)			
2000	0	-	-	N/A	N/A	3,937,863	13.62	57	0	1,067,660,000.00
2001	0	-	-	N/A	N/A	6,816,685	73.11	N/A	0	1,607,700,000.00
2002	405	-	10.43	3,995,306	109,722	4,105,028	-39.78	68	1,070,000,000.00	-500,000,000.00
2003	549	35.56	8.18	4,493,789	89,716	4,583,505	11.66	72	1,610,000,000.00	-350,000,000.00
2004	504	-8.20	8.01	N/A	N/A	4,693,860	2.41	47	1,500,000,000.00	1,392,016,736.91
2005	495	-1.79	9.01	N/A	N/A	6,310,575	34.44	55	2,160,000,000.00	-758,747,616.93
2006	843	70.30	8.01	7,208,318	163,644	7,371,962	16.82	73	2,074,050,126.96	422,144,319.21
2007	1,133	34.40	7.01	10,046,217	257,043	10,303,260	39.76	87	688,219,408.70	1,762,684,912.45
2008	1,318	16.33	7.01	11,007,771	507,852	11,515,623	11.77	54	870,139,980.09	1,614,374,694.67
2009	1,359	3.11	6.6	12,946,927	594,089	13,541,016	17.59	72	2,362,863,809.79	1,035,707,561.19
2010	1,497	10.16	5.62	13,839,836	640,002	14,479,838	6.93	73	2,274,234,063.17	1,421,400,000.00
2011	1,628	8.75	4.27	15,583,779	646,812	16,230,591	12.09	65	1,784,507,561.19	859,034,092.00
2012	1,508	-7.37	5.26	14,515,229	703,995	15,219,224	-6.23	70	2,350,000,000.00	2,284,496,958.22
2013	1,608	6.63	4.35	15,357,933	710,952	16,068,885	5.58	68	1,833,295,160.00	1,257,799,888.93
2014	1,698	5.60	3.98	16,483,099	1,020,208	17,503,307	8.93	65	3,065,095,616.83	1,108,485,952.53
2015	1,656	-2.47	4.13	15,195,464	1,092,629	16,288,093	-6.94	54	1,877,209,453.93	2,502,617,466.03
2016	1,559	-5.86	3.51	14,742,232	906,687	15,648,919	-3.92	55	1,774,072,969.95	1,067,660,000.00
2017	1,307	-16.16	3.99	14,580,670	883,715	15,464,385	-1.18	56	3,375,371,801.91	1,607,700,000.00

Source: Tin Can Island Port Complex (TCIPC) Annual Report 2003, 2007 – 2017

In analyzing pre and post concession port performance of the TCIP, this study relied on Pinwa's (1999) dissertation which measured landlord model performance at the Onne port using growth rate analysis. Hence, the research findings on TCIP's Ships/Vessels used growth rate of ship traffic, average turnaround time, cargo throughput, container throughput, vehicular traffic, berth occupancy rate and financial performance to analyze pre and post concession performance of TCIP.

Before the concession of the TCIP, the annual growth rate was between 35-70% due to the wide margin in number of ships that entered the port. The annual growth rate of ship traffic after the concession was at 34.40% in 2007 and it dipped further, recording a negative rate in 2017 and for three consecutive years from 2015-2017. The pre-concession (2002-2006) growth rate was 108.15% while the post-concession period recorded 15.36% growth, revealing how port concession had little impact on ship traffic.

The average turnaround time for these vessels after offloading their cargo was 10.43 days in 2002, it only reduced by two days in 2006 which was during the pre-concession period. As at 2017, the average turnaround time for ships has reduced to four days. The growth rate of turnaround time during pre-concession was -23.20% but post-concession growth rate is at -43.08%, in this case, the negative growth is a progressive impact for the TCIP, as it means, ships can leave the ports within ninety-six hours after docking and offloading.

In 2001, TCIP recorded a total cargo throughput of 6,816,685 tonnes with a growth rate of 73% but it dropped in 2003 to a negative growth rate. However, TCIP recorded a 34% growth rate in cargo throughput in 2005 with 6,310,575 tonnes, this was before port concession started in 2006. The table above showed that the highest growth rate recorded after port concession became operational was 39.76% in 2007 and it was continued to spiral downward from that point to logging negative growth rate from 2015 to 2017. TCIP recorded an overall 87% growth rate in pre-concession while it had 50.1% growth in post-concession period. The unavailability of complete data on cargo types handled at the TCIP prevented the researcher for analyzing the growth rate of dry bulk, liquid bulk, container and general cargo.

The berth occupancy rate at the port was at 73% in 2006, which implies that there was congestion at the TCIP. After the concession, TCIP had a breakeven berth occupancy rate in 2008, since then it has stayed within the 50 – 70% range hovering between full utilization and underutilization. TCIP's generated revenue was over a billion naira before the government conceived the idea of port reforms, but it started having operational deficit when its expenditure surpassed generated revenue in 2004, which could be attributed to the labour issues and workforce downsizing when the process for port concession began. After TCIP experienced the last operational deficit in 2007, it has maintained a favourable balance of payment, netting billions of naira minus expenditure.

From analyzing ships/vessels performance at the TCIP using ship traffic, average turnaround time, cargo throughput, berth occupancy rate and financial performance, the conclusion is that port concession only had slight impact on port performance as shown by the annual growth rate. Before concession, port operations and administration were in shambles but what was observed during fieldwork showed that there is a sense of order at the port these days. The functions of each stakeholder and actors in port operations at the TCIP are mapped out now.

Questionnaires administered and interviews conducted under the themes of Port Terminals Patronage; Port Resources; Port Infrastructure; and Port Authorities and Service Delivery Issues revealed that TCIP which represents the NPA at the port is only concerned with collecting charges from shippers and private terminals, raising manifests and providing the needed amenities like equipment, infrastructure facilities; the terminal operators receive these cargoes from the ships, provide warehousing for it, deliver or release it to the owner with proper documentations and receive payment for the services rendered; and the Customs collect excise duties from clearing agents as well as perform the functions of inspection of cargoes and vessels that come to the port with other regulatory agencies such as NDLEA, NAFDAC, NESREA.

Data gathered on port resources revealed that cargo clearance procedures have been reduced to accommodate current situations in the country and make goods leave the port faster, before concession, it took weeks or months before an agent will be able to clear their cargoes but it has considerably reduced now. Warehouse facilities including bonded terminals and off-dock warehouses are being used to clear port traffic and make services more seamless. Before concession, transportation of cargo took months due to congestion, but these days, it has considerably reduced. Port operations like generating manifest, waybill, payment of customs duties and clearing cargoes at terminals have become automated and have proper documentation, unlike the non-documentation of activities or vessels leading to loss of cargoes witnessed in the era before the concession.

Observations during fieldwork revealed that private terminals have invested in heavy-duty machines like forklift, RTGs, to boost their operations and competitiveness among each other, while also running 24/7 operations at the port in TCIP, backlogs of cargoes are non-existent, except for unclaimed ones. It was also noted that private terminals invested in infrastructure to meet up with international best practices in port operations and invested in safety to protect port workers.

The data on port infrastructure and resources also shows that they could get better, for instance, there is still delay in cargo clearance, exorbitant charges for clearance of cargo by the Customs, lack of infrastructure on the part of the NPA and federal government that has failed to make quay apron, scanners and other equipment available. The most daunting issue gotten from the collated data remains inaccessible roads to the port areas and the government's culpability.

In recent times, the federal government has implemented some proactive measures to address the issue of congestion and inaccessible roads at the Lagos ports such as Completion of the Apapa rail extension into the port area, Construction of Tin Can trailer parks, Introduction of an electronic call-up system known as ETO to reduce trailers on port roads, and Diversion of vessels to Eastern ports. However, these measures have not been quite successful in arresting the port congestion at the Lagos ports and other technical and administrative issues.

4.5 Verification of Research Assumptions

The study used a mixed method of research, hence, the need to also analyze and verify research assumptions using the data gotten from questionnaires administered to port users and interviews conducted with port personnel.

The first assumption states that 'adoption of PPP had a positive or negative impact on service delivery at TCIP.' Data shows that the impact has been positive and negative which is shown in Table 4.4. Cargo throughput and ship traffic had better growth rate in post concession period

than it was obtained in post-concession period. These two indicators also recorded negative annual growth rate for three consecutive years during post-concession period, which buttresses that concession has slight impact on port performance. On the positive side, there has been a significant drop in ship waiting time which has reduced from ten days in pre-concession period to four days in post-concession period while berth occupancy rate has shown figures that implies break-even utilization of port. To sway the scale for positive impact, there has been significant increase in revenue generated at the TCIP after the concession.

The second assumption states that ‘the concession of the terminals enhanced cargo clearance procedures at TCIP.’ To analyze this assumption, the study focused on indices within port resources such as clearance procedure, handling rate of discharge operation, waiting time and operating cost. Data gotten from the questionnaires and interviews revealed that the stakeholders at the port have digitized their operations and improved cargo clearance procedures after the concession, asserting the assumption as ‘true.’ However, same data revealed that there are still concerns about delays in cargo clearing at TCIP.

The third assumption states that ‘the concession of TCIP increased revenue generation at the TCIP.’ This assumption was tested with financial performance of the port. The revenue generated during pre-concession surpassed two billion in naira and over ten million in dollars, this is was in 2006 when the ports were handed over to the private terminal operators. But, the TCIP was generated more revenue in pre-concession period, recording over three billion in naira and over one fifty million in dollars. Also, operational deficit was recorded twice, 2004 and 2005 during pre-concession while it was only recorded once in 2007, a year after the concession, since then operational surplus to the tune of two billion naira has been recorded multiple times.

The last assumption states that ‘the concession of TCIP terminals improved infrastructural facilities within the port and its environs.’ This was verified and turned out to be partly true

when data from port infrastructure and service delivery issues was analyzed. Port users and personnel opined that there was an improvement in port facilities and machinery, but they cited issues such as inaccessible roads to port areas and its environs as a huge challenge. Observations during fieldwork revealed that infrastructure facilities like roads and provision of certain equipment within the domain of the federal government and NPA is lagging and affecting port operations at the TCIP.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter gives a detailed summary of why the study of Nigerian ports was embarked on, how data was collected and analyzed to measure the impact of concession on service delivery at TCIP and outlines recommendations suitable to counter the challenges observed at the TCIP.

5.2 Summary

This study set out to do an impact assessment of PPP on service delivery at Nigerian ports, it chose to use the TCIP as a case study is one of the most viable ports in the country. The research on port concession at TCIP was conducted using a mixed method of research while analyzing before and after-effects of the port concession on its operations.

Data collated from the annual reports of the TCIP such as ships that entered the port, cargo throughput, container throughput, container traffic, vehicular traffic, berth occupancy and turnaround time for vessels and ships for a period of seventeen years (2000 – 2017) was analyzed using line and scattered charts to get Port Performance before and after concession, interpretation of the result showed that concession had a positive impact on port performance and increased government revenue but it could get better if certain measures are put in place.

The primary source of data collected through administering questionnaires to port users (clearing and forwarding agents, shipping company staff and truck drivers) and triangulated with interviews conducted with port personnel (NPA TCIP staff, TCIP Customs Command staff and Terminal operators' staff) to analyze the impact of concession on service delivery at TCIP showed that cargo clearance procedure improved, transportation of cargo improved, warehouse facilities were improved, heavy-duty equipment was invested in by terminal

operators, automation of documentation and payment, cargoes were accounted for. However, issues such as delay in cargo clearance, exorbitant charge for cargo clearance, lack of equipment and inaccessible roads to port areas and terminals are challenges that continue to plague port operations and administration at the TCIP.

5.3. Conclusion

Unilateral study of the TCIP showed challenges unique to the port area, making the recommendations given distinctive to it, unlike when it is studied alongside others and the recommendations given are not reflective of the challenges faced at that particular port.

The data analyzed during this research showed that port concession has given Nigeria the needed level playing ground for elevation to the top 50 busiest port in the world (Lagos ports is among the top 5 busiest port in West Africa and Africa).

5.4. Recommendations

Data collected and analyzed for this study showed that port operation fared better after concession at the TCIP but challenges such as delay in cargo clearance, exorbitant charge for cargo clearance, lack of equipment and inaccessible roads to port areas and terminals continue to affect service delivery in its operations.

The researcher posited that to curb the aforesaid challenges and improve service delivery at the TCIP, recommendations discussed below should be administered to port operations at the TCIP and other port complexes facing the same challenge.

- 1. Introduction of New Technology and Practices:** The NPA needs to make the National Single Window (NSW) platform operative. The NSW is an initiative of the port authority that collapse procedures involved in cargo clearing into a single platform

managed by the NPA. NSW will drive full automation of the port operations which will go a long way to reduce corruption.

- 2. Regulation of operations through new policy rules and procedures:** The terminal operators complained about an annual increase in throughput fees and other dues which harms their turnout, hence, there is a need for government to review these fees. There is also the need to create a fiscal policy directive that makes FOREX stable for port operations, especially for its stakeholders and shippers.
- 3. Improvement of Infrastructure:** State of emergency needs to be declared on all the roads leading to the port, while the rehabilitation and reconstruction of some of these roads need to be hastened up. The construction work on railway lines should be hastened up, dry ports construction should be completed quickly while equipment needed to boost service delivery at the port should be provided by the stakeholders.
- 4. Curbing Corruption:** There is also a need for the government to give proactive directives to clear out people traffic at port areas, especially the touts inhabiting the port areas as they are part of new breeders of corruption within port operations.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A

Questionnaire administered to Port Users (English Version)

Department of Political Science and
International Studies,
Faculty of Social Sciences,
Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria – Nigeria.
8th May 2019.

Dear respondent,

A QUESTIONNAIRE ON ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP (CONCESSION) ON SERVICE DELIVERY OF THE NIGERIAN PORTS: A CASE STUDY OF TIN CAN ISLAND PORT, LAGOS STATE

I am Muideen O. Mohammed, a postgraduate in the Department of Political Science and International Studies, Ahmadu Bello, Zaria – Nigeria. As part of the conditions for the award of Master of Science (M.Sc.) in Political Science from the above named institution, I am conducting a research on “Assessment of the Impact of Public-Private Partnership (Concession) on Service Delivery of the Nigerian Ports: A Case Study of Tin Can Island Port, Lagos State.” I shall be very grateful if you will do me a favour by completing the attached questionnaire as objective as possible.

Please be assured that any information given in this regard will be treated with utmost confidentiality and used only for the purpose of this academic exercise.

You are not being forced to participate in this exercise and if at a point you feel uncomfortable with your participation you are free to opt out.

Thanks for your unreserved assistance.

Tick [✓] in the boxes provided to verify your response to the questions or write your response in the space provided and feel free to leave any questions blank. Thank you for your cooperation.

PART A: Background Detail

1. Gender: Male [] Female []
2. Age: 18 – 29 [] 30 – 39 [] 40 – 49 [] 50 – above []
3. Marital status: Single [] Married [] Divorced [] Widowed []
4. Educational Qualification: Non-formal/Adult Education [] Primary []
Secondary [] Tertiary [] Others [] please specify _____
5. Employment: Freight Forwarder/Clearing Agent [] Shipping Company Staff []
Driver [] Others [] please specify _____

PART B: Impact of Concession on Service Delivery at TCIP

6. How long have you been using the Tin Can Island Port (TCIP)? Less than 1 year []
1 – 5 years [] 6 – 10 years [] 11 years – above []
7. Which port terminal do you frequent at the TCIP?
Five Star Logistics Limited [] Josepdam Ports Services Limited [] Ports and Cargo
Handling Services Limited (SIFAX Group) [] Port and Terminal Multiservices
Limited (PTML) [] Tin Can Container Terminal Limited [] Kirikiri Lighter
Terminal I&II (KLT) []
8. How long does it take you to clear your cargo at the port terminal? Days [] ____
Weeks [] ____ Months [] ____
9. Is the clearance procedure at the port better after the concession? Yes [] No []
Indifferent []
10. What range of amount do you pay to clear goods at the port? ₦10,000 - ₦50,000 []
₦51,000 – ₦100,000 [] ₦101,000 – ₦200,000 [] ₦201,000 – ₦500,000 []
₦501,000 – above []
11. Where do you pay more for clearance of the cargo? NPA (TCIPC) Admin []
Shipping Company [] Nigeria Customs Service [] Terminal Operators []
12. Asides from agencies listed in No. 11, which other agencies do you pay to clear cargo
at the port? _____
13. Do you wish to pay lesser for cargo clearance at the port? Yes [] No [] Indifferent []
14. Where do you wish to pay lesser for clearance of the cargo? NPA (TCIPC) Admin []
Shipping Company [] Nigeria Customs Service [] Terminal Operators [] All of
the above []

15. Which warehouse facility do you use at the port? Terminal Operators' Warehouse []
NPA Tin Can Warehouse [] Clearing Agents' Warehouse [] Others [] please
specify_____
16. Is transport of cargo from the port better after the concession? Yes [] No []
Indifferent []
17. How long does it take you to transport your cargo from the port after clearance? Days
[] ___ Weeks [] ___ Months [] ___
18. Where do you experience more challenges when clearing your cargo at the port?
NPA (TCIPC) Admin [] Shipping Company [] Nigeria Customs Service []
Terminal Operators [] All of the above []
19. What do you think causes the challenges you experience when clearing your cargo at
the port? Corruption [] Delay by Staff [] Lack of manpower [] Lack of
infrastructure facilities [] All of the above []
20. Which of these actors needs more staff to improve their service delivery at the port?
NPA (TCIPC) Admin [] Nigeria Customs Service [] Terminal Operators [] All
of the above []
21. Does inaccessible roads to the port also cause challenges when clearing cargo at the
port? Yes [] No [] Maybe []
22. If you are a driver, please answer this, how long have you been on the queue with the
other drivers to clear your cargo at the port? Days [] ___ Weeks [] ___ Months [] ___
23. After the completion of the railway line that leads to the port, will you use it to
transport cargo from the port? Yes [] No [] Indifferent []

Appendix B

Questionnaire administered to Port Users (Pidgin English Version)

Department of Political Science and International Studies,

Faculty of Social Sciences,

Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria – Nigeria.

8th May 2019.

Dear respondent,

QUESTIONNAIRE WEY DEY ASSESS DI IMPACT WEY PUBLIC-PRIVATE COLLABORATION GET ONTOP SERVICE DELIVERY OF DI NIGERIAN PORTS: MY FOCUS DEY ON TIN CAN ISLAND PORT, LAGOS STATE.

My name na Muideen O. Mohammed, I be postgraduate student for di Department of Political Science and International Studies, Ahmadu Bello, Zaria – Nigeria. Becoz say e dey part of the things wey I must do to collect the award of Master of Science (M.Sc.) in Political Science, I dey conduct dis research to “assess di impact wey public-private collaboration get ontop service delivery of di Nigerian ports: I dey focus on tin can island port, wey dey Lagos state. I go dey very grateful if you hep me complete the questionnaire wey I attach with truthfulness.

Abeg dey assure say any informate wey you give me go dey confidential and na only dis research I go use am do.

No be by force to take part for dis exercise and if you reach a point wey you no feel comfortable to continue, you dey free to stop.

Thank you say you assist me.

Tick [✓] for di box wey I provide to torchlight your ansa to di question or make you write your answer for di space wey I provide, you dey free to waka pass any question wey you no too sabi. Thank you say you dey corporate with me.

PART A: Background Informate

1. Gender: Boy [] Girl []
2. Age: 18 – 29 [] 30 – 39 [] 40 – 49 [] 50 – above []
3. Marital status: Single [] Married [] Divorced [] Widowed []
4. Educational Qualification: Non-formal/Adult Education [] Primary []
Secondary [] Tertiary [] Others [] abeg write am _____

5. Employment: Clearing and forwarding Agent [] Staff for Shipping Company []
Driver [] Others [] abeg write am _____

PART B: Impact wey Concession get ontop Service Delivery at TCIP

6. E don reach how many years wey you don dey use Tin Can Island Port (TCIP)? E neva reach 1 year [] 1 – 5 years [] 6 – 10 years [] 11 years – above []
7. Which port terminal you dey go most for TCIP? Five Star Logistics Limited []
Josepdam Ports Services Limited [] Ports and Cargo Handling Services Limited
(SIFAX Group) [] Port and Terminal Multiservices Limited (PTML) [] Tin
Can Container Terminal Limited [] Kirikiri Lighter Terminal I&II (KLT) []
8. E dey take you reach how long to clear your cargo for di port terminal? Days [] ___
Weeks [] ___ Months [] ___
9. Shey you fit talk say di procedure wey you dey follow when you wan clear for di port
don dey better after di concession? Yes [] No [] I no fit say []
10. Di money wey you dey pay when you wan clear goods for di port dey between how
much to how much? ₦10,000 - ₦50,000 [] ₦51,000 – ₦100,000 [] ₦101,000 –
₦200,000 [] ₦201,000 – ₦500,000 [] ₦501,000 – above []
11. Na where you dey pay most when you wan clear your cargo? NPA (TCIPC) Admin []
Shipping Company [] Nigeria Customs Service [] Terminal Operators []
12. Apart from the agencies wey I list for No. 11, na for which other agencies you dey pay
when you wan clear your cargo for di port? _____
13. Shey you wish say make the money wey you dey pay when you wan clear your cargo
for di port reduce? Yes [] No [] I no mind []
14. Na where you wish say make them reduce the money wey you dey pay when you wan
clear your cargo? NPA (TCIPC) Admin [] Shipping Company [] Nigeria
Customs Service [] Terminal Operators [] All of them []
15. Na which warehouse facility you dey use for di port? Dem Terminal Operators
Warehouse [] Dem NPA Tin Can Warehouse [] Dem Clearing Agents Warehouse []
Others [] abeg write am _____
16. Shey you fit talk say to transport cargo from di port don better after di concession? Yes
[] No [] I no fy say []
17. Like how long e dey take you to transport your cargo from di port after you don clear
am? Days [] ___ Weeks [] ___ Months [] ___

18. Na where you dey face plenty wahala pass when you wan clear your cargo for di port? NPA (TCIPC) Admin [] Shipping Company [] Nigeria Customs Service [] Terminal Operators [] All of them []
19. Wetin you feel say dey cause di wahala wey you dey face when you wan clear your cargo for di port? Corruption [] Delay wey staff dey cause [] manpower wey no reach [] infrastructure facilities wey no dey [] All of them []
20. Na which area you feel say need more staff if dem want make deir service delivery dey better for di port? NPA (TCIPC) Admin [] Nigeria Customs Service [] Terminal Operators [] All of them []
21. Shey di road wey reach di port wey don bad dey among di things wey dey cause wahala when you dey clear your cargo for di port? Yes [] No [] E fit be so []
22. If you be driver abeg answer dis question, e don reach how long wey you don dey queue with di other drivers onto say you wan clear your cargo for di port? Days [] __ Weeks [] __ Months [] __
23. After dem finish the railway line wey reach di port, shey you go dey use am when you wan transport your cargo from di port? Yes [] No [] I fit use am and I fit no use am []

Appendix C

Questionnaire administered to Port Users (Yoruba Version)

Department of Political Science and International
Studies,

Faculty of Social Sciences,

Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria – Nigeria.

8th May 2019.

Afèsì mi ọwón,

ÌBÉÈRÈ LÁTI TỌPIPI IPA TI ÌFỌWỌSOWỌPỌ ÌJỌBA ÀTI ÀDÁNI NÍ LÓRI ÌJÁFÁFÁ
ÌŞÉ ÀWỌN IBÚDÓ NÀÌJÍRÌÀ: ÀGBÉYÈWỌ IBÚDÓ TIN CAN NI ÌLÚ ÈKÓ.

Orúkọ mi ni Muideen O. Mohammed, mo je akẹkọ ní ẹka imọ nípa ọ̀şẹ̀lú àti àgbáyé ní Ahmadu Bello, Zaria – Nàìjíríà. Gégé bíi ara oun tí mo gbódò ẹ láti gba oyè Master of Science (M.Sc.) nínu imọ nípa ọ̀şẹ̀lú ní ilé ẹkọ tí mo dárúko síwájú, mò n ẹ ẹ ẹ iwádi lóri “ipa ti ifowosowopọ ijoba ati adani ni lori ijafafa ise awon ibudó Nàìjíríà: Àgbéyèwọ ibudó Tin Can ni ilú ẹkọ”. Inú mi á dùn tí o bálè dáhùn àwọn ibéèrè isàlẹ yí pèlú òtító.

Mò n fún ẹ ní idálójú pé gbogbo idáhùn ẹ jé oun àşírí tó ma jé lílò fún ẹ iwádi yí nikan.

Ìkọpa ẹ nínu dídáhùn àwọn ibéèrè yí kii ẹ tipátipá, tí o bá si bá idáhùn náà dé ibikan tí kò sí wù ọ ẹ mọ, àyè wà fún ọ láti má tẹsíwájú.

O ẹ fún iránlówó ẹ.

Fi àmi [✓] sí àwọn àpótí tí a pèsè láti ẹ atọka idáhùn ẹ tàbí kí o kọ idáhùn ẹ sí àyè tí a pèsè, o sí lè fi ibéèrè tí o kò bá mò sílẹ. Oşé fún ifowosowopọ ẹ.

APÁ KINÍ: Àlàyè abéle

1. jẹndà: ọkùnrin [] obìnrin []
2. ọjó orí: méjídínlógún sí mọkàndínlógbón [] ọgbón sí mọkàndínlógòjì [] ọgòjì sí mọkàndínláàdọta [] àdọta àti jùbẹ̀lẹ []
3. ipò ìgbéyàwó: Àpón [] Mo ní aya/ọkọ [] Mo ti kọ aya/ọkọ sílẹ [] opó []
4. Oyè ẹkọ: ẹkọ àgbà/mi ò lọ ilé iwé [] ilé iwé àkóbèrè [] ilé iwé girama [] ilé iwé gíga [] òmíràn [] dákun şàlàyè _____
5. Işé: A yanjúerù ibudó [] Ọşíşé ilé işé aferù ránşé [] Awakò [] Ọmíràn [] Dákun şàlàyè _____

APÁ KEJÌ: Ipa ti ifowosowopò ni lóri ijáfáfá işé àwọn ibùdó Tin Can ni ilú èkó (TCIP)

6. Óti tó igbàwo tí o ti n lo ibùdó fún agolo onírín ni Island, èkó? Kò tìl tó odún kan [] odún kan si odún márùn [] odún mēfà si odún mēwà [] odún mókànlá àti jùbèèlò []
7. Èbúté ibùdó TCIP wo lo ma n ló jù? Five Star Logistics Limited [] Josepdam Ports Services Limited [] Ports and Cargo Handling Services Limited (SIFAX Group) [] Port and Terminal Multiservices Limited (PTML) [] Tin Can Container Terminal Limited [] Kirikiri Lighter Terminal I&II (KLT) []
8. Báwo ló se ma n pé tó kí o tó rí erù rẹ yanjú ní èbúté ibùdó? ojó [] _____ ọsẹ [] _____ oşù [] _____
9. Sé ilàna àti rí erù yanjú ní ibùdó dára si léyìn ifowosowopò ijoba àti àdani? bèni [] bèkò [] mi kò lè sọ []
10. Bii élò ni o ma n san láti rí erù rẹ yanjú ní ibùdó? egbèrún mēwà si egbèrún lónà àádòta [] egbèrún lónà àádòta ó lékan sí egbèrún lónà ogórún [] egbèrún lónà ogórún ó lékan sí egbèrún lónà ogófà [] egbèrún lónà ogófà ó lékan sí egbèrún lónà èdègbèta [] egbèrún lónà èdègbèta ó lékan àti jùbèèlò []
11. Ibo lo ti ma n sanwó to pòjù láti yanjú erù rẹ? ọdò àwọn olùdarí ibùdó (TCIPC) [] ilé işé tí a n fi erù rán [] ilé işé kòstòm [] ọdò àwọn ọsìşé èbúté []
12. Yàtò sí àwọn ilé işé tí a dárúkọ sòkè, ibo lo tú ti ma n sanwó láti yanjú erù rẹ ní ibùdó?

13. Sé ó wù ó kí owó yíyanjú erù tí ò n san ní ibùdó dínkù? bèni [] bèkò [] mi kò lè sọ []
14. Ibo ló ti wù ó kí wón ti dín owó to ma n san kù? ọdò àwọn olùdarí ibùdó (TCIPC) [] ilé işé tí a n fi erù rán [] ilé işé kòstòm [] ọdò àwọn ọsìşé èbúté [] gbogbo wón []
15. Yàrá ikójàsí wo ni o má n lò ní ibùdó? Yàrá ikójàsí àwọn ọsìşé èbúté [] Yàrá ikójàsí ibùdó Tin Can ni ilú èkó [] Yàrá ikójàsí àwọn tí n yanjú erù [] ibòmíràn [] dákun şàlàyé _____
16. Léyìn ifowosowopò, se o ti wa rorùn si láti kó erù kúrò ní ibùdó? bèni [] bèkò [] mi kò lè sọ []
17. Báwo ló se ma n pé tó kí o tó rí erù rẹ kó kúrò ní ibùdó léyìn to bá tí yanjú wón? ojó [] _____ ọsẹ [] _____ oşù [] _____
18. Ibo lo ti ma n kojú işòro jù tí o bá fẹ yanjú àwọn erù rẹ ní ibùdó? ọdò àwọn olùdarí ibùdó (TCIPC) [] ilé işé tí a n fi erù rán [] ilé işé kòstòm [] ọdò àwọn ọsìşé èbúté [] gbogbo wón []
19. Kílo rò pé ó ma n şe okùnfa àwọn işòro tí o ma n dojúkọ tí o bá fẹ yanjú àwọn erù rẹ ní ibùdó? ibàjé [] Ìdádúró lá tọwọ ọwọn ọsìşé [] àìní ọsìşé tó pòtò [] àìní àwọn oun amáyéderùn [] gbogbo wón []
20. Èwo nínú àwọn èka wònyí ni kí ó gba ọsìşé si láti jékí işé wón dára si? àwọn olùdarí ibùdó (TCIPC) [] ilé işé kòstòm [] àwọn ọsìşé èbúté [] gbogbo wón []
21. Sé ọnà àtidé ibùdó tí kò da pèlù àwọn oun tí n fa işòro tí o bá fẹ yanjú àwọn erù rẹ ní ibùdó? bèni [] bèkò [] bóyá []
22. Tí o bájé awakò, dákun dáhùn ibèèrè yí, o ti to igbawo to ti wa lori tito pèlù àwọn awakò tó kù láti yanjú àwọn erù rẹ ní ibùdó? ojó [] _____ ọsẹ [] _____ oşù [] _____
23. Tí wón bá ti parí ojú irin tó dé ibùdó, se o ma lòó láti kó erù rẹ láti ibùdó? bèni [] bèkò [] mi kò lè sọ []

Appendix D

Interview Questions for NPA Administration at the TCIP

1. Did the state of Nigerian ports warrant for the government to hand it over to the private operators?
2. What is your opinion on the concession of the port to private operators?
3. Has service delivery improved since private terminals took over the terminal, if yes, how?
4. Does private terminals have infrastructures that can improve their service delivery?
5. Does lack of manpower, accessible road or both cause low service delivery at port terminals?
6. Will you say that there is no corruption or excess delay at the port and that it does not affect service delivery?
7. What is the NPA doing as regards accessible roads and long queue of trailers at the TCIP?
8. What other infrastructure as the NPA failed to provide in order to improve operations of the private terminals?
9. Does NPA regulate employment and training of staff employed by private operators?
10. Is there a percentage line for payment of rent or they pay uniform rents?
11. What are the other dues that terminal operators pay besides rent?
12. Do terminal operators default on the payment of their dues and rent to the NPA, if yes, how?
13. How much does the NPA charge for clearance of cargo at the port?
14. What has the NPA done as regards the clearance fees charged by terminal operators and customs?

15. How does the NPA plan to improve on the performance recorded at the port during this concession period?
16. Why was the concession agreement for some terminal operators extended?
17. Does the NPA have a transition plan in place for handing over of terminals after concession expires or it is open to renegotiation?
18. Has the recent Presidential Directive to decongest the port roads affected service delivery, if yes, how?
19. Besides, the railway transport leading to Lagos port and granting tax concession to Dangote Group to construct alternate roads to the port, what other areas is the FG, NPA or ICRC exploring to improve service delivery at the TCIP?
20. What is the success recorded from the Single Window Platform introduced by the NPA?
21. In terms of heavy-duty infrastructure, what is the plan to provide more, like the Scanners that will improve service delivery and cutout excess delay at the port?
22. What is your opinion on the revenue generated by Nigeria port, is it enough or it can be better?

Appendix E

Interview Question for Customs TCIP Command

1. Did the state of Nigerian ports warrant for the government to hand it over to the private operators?
2. What is your opinion on the concession of the port to private operators?
3. Has service delivery improved since private terminals took over the terminal, if yes, how?
4. Does private terminals have infrastructures that can improve their service delivery?
5. How long does it take the Customs to inspect cargoes at terminal?
6. What does the Customs check for while inspecting cargoes at the terminals?
7. What equipment does the Customs use to inspect cargoes at the terminals?
8. Recently, the FG approved the purchase of scanners, has the scanners arrived and become operational at the various terminals?
9. What can you say about Duplication of duties and functions at the port terminal by govt. agencies?
10. What is the major cause of excess delay or turnaround time for drivers taking delivery of cargoes at the port?
11. How does the Customs know what to charge as clearance fee for cargoes before it leaves the port?
12. Is it the container size/content or type of shipment that determines clearance fee charged by Customs?
13. The fluctuating exchange rate, how does it affect cargo clearance at the port?
14. Does the Customs also collect dues/charges from private terminals? If yes, what are these charges/dues?

15. Is it only customs authorized agents that comes for cargo clearance or just anyone who has cargo to clear?
16. The Presidential Directive to decongest port, how has it affected Customs operations at the port?
17. What is the Customs doing to ensure faster clearance of cargoes at the port terminals?
18. How does the NPA and Customs work together to improve on operations and faster clearance of cargo and its movement from the port?
19. The revenue generated by Customs at TCIP has improved since port concession but is there room for more improvement?
20. What are the steps being taken by Customs to generate more revenue for the federal government at the port?

Appendix F

Interview Questions for Private Terminal Operators' Staff

1. When did this terminal become operational?
2. Did you renovate the terminal or build from the scratch after it was handed over to your company under the concession agreement?
3. What was the state of the port before you took over its management in terms of service delivery?
4. What are the challenges faced when operations began at your terminal and how did you get over it?
5. Are you still within the range of the original concession contract or has it been extended?
6. What are the services provided by your terminal to port users?
7. How long does it take to clear cargo/products from your terminal and the procedures involved?
8. What is the price range for clearing cargo/products at your terminal?
9. Does your terminal have specialty in terms of cargo/product that makes it to your terminal?
10. How much do you make monthly/annually from operating this terminal and how much is the rent and dues paid to the management of TCIP?
11. Has rent/dues increased or decreased since you began operations at the port terminal?
12. Has services delivery in terms of clearance of cargo improve since concession of these port terminals to you and other private terminals?
13. Does the NPA or NCS improve or create challenges to clearance at your terminal, if yes, how?

14. Besides the NPA or NCS, which other agencies affects or help improve service delivery at your terminal?
15. At your terminal, what affects service delivery in terms of clearing of cargo at the port?
16. Does lack of manpower, accessible road or both cause low service delivery at your port terminal?
17. Is corruption and excess delay during cargo clearance lead to low service delivery at your terminal?
18. What have you been doing at your terminal to improve on service delivery and what is the outcome?
19. How can the NPA or TCIP assist you to improve on service delivery at your terminal?
20. The recent Presidential Directive to decongest the port roads, how has it affected service delivery at your terminal?
21. What do you want the NPA or govt. to do, besides road const., to help you improve service delivery?

Appendix G

List of people interviewed

S/N	NAME	ORGANISATION/ TERMINAL	RANK/POSITION	DATE OF INTERVIEW
1	Mr. Suraju	NPA TCIPC Office	Personal Assistant to Port Manager (PA-PM)	June 25, 2019
2	Mrs. P. Umar	NPA TCIPC Office	Port Legal Adviser (PLA)	July 11, 2019
3	Mr. Abdulkadir	NPA TCIP Office	Chief Tariff and Billing Officer (CTBO)	September 25, 2019
4	Supr. Uche Ejesieme	NCS TCIP Command	Customs Public Relations Officer (PRO)	October 7, 2019
5	*	Josepdam Port Serv.	Commercial Manager	October 7, 2019
6	*	Josepdam Port Serv.	Port Statistician	October 7, 2019
7	*	Five Star Logistics	Head of Documentation	October 10, 2019
8	*	Five Star Logistics	Head of Customer Care	October 10, 2019

* The staff of these private terminals requested that their names not to be in print or on record.

Appendix H

List of Figures

Figure 1: Ship Traffic and Gross Registered Tonnage (GRT) at the TCIP, 2000–2017

Figure 2: Total Cargo Throughput (Inward and Outward) at the TCIP 2000 – 2017

Figure 3: Berth Occupancy Rate at the TCIP 2000 – 2017

